

TRANSNATURE

Interview Report

Anonymized

Case: Julian Alps

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1 Introduction

Contains general information about the case study (based on desk research undertaken before the interview phase and some aspects of the introduction questions posed in the interview)

Eurac's case study focuses on the Julian Alps,¹ that is the transboundary cooperation on biodiversity conservation existing between the Triglav National Park (TNP)² in Slovenia (SI) and Parco Naturale Prealpi Giulie (PNPG)³ in Italy (IT). This cooperation is institutionalized within the framework of different and overlapping cooperation schemes, that are the Transboundary Ecoregion program⁴ and the European Charter of Sustainable Tourism (ECST) of EUROPARC Federation,⁵ as well as a UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve officialized in July 2024 and made out of the preexisting Italian and Slovenian national MAB

Reserves. The story of this cooperation and its geographic extension are explained in the following.

The Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve is made of the two national Biosphere Reserves that include two key parks: the TNP in Slovenia and the PNPG in Italy, each with a distinct history and role within the larger Biosphere Reserve. The TNP is Slovenia's only national park and one of Europe's oldest protected areas. Its origins date back to 1924 when it was established as the Alpine Conservation Park in the Triglav Lakes Valley, covering 1,600 hectares. Over time, the park expanded, and in 1961 it was renamed as TNP, with its area increased to 2,000 hectares. A significant milestone occurred in 1981 with the enactment of new legislation that defined the park's boundaries more comprehensively. Further expansions were introduced in 2010, incorporating settlements such as *Kneške ravne* and surrounding areas. Today, the TNP spans nearly the entire Eastern Julian Alps, covering 84,000 hectares, which represents about four percent of Slovenia's total land area.

On the Italian side, the PNPG was formally established in 1996 through Friuli Venezia Giulia (FVG) Regional Law No. 42/96. Indeed, efforts to create a protected area in this region began much earlier, with discussions starting in the 1970s. The first concrete proposal for a park in the Prealps appeared in the FVG Regional Urban Plan of 1978, which envisioned a large regional park between Gemona del Friuli, Taipana, and the Resia Valley. Intense debates throughout the 1980s about the park's boundaries and management eventually led to a scaled-down version of the park becoming operational by the late 1980s. Before its formal establishment, a coordination committee involving municipalities such as Chiusaforte, Moggio Udinese, Resia, Resiutta, and Venzone oversaw early initiatives, including environmental education and the restoration of old structures for visitors.

Transboundary collaboration between the Alpine clubs across the Italian, Slovenian, and Austrian borders for rescue operations or thematic initiatives and meetings existed before the creation of the PNPG. Therefore, cooperation between the PNPG and the TNP built on existing ties and was increasingly strengthened throughout the years. Soon after the official creation of the PNPG, the first joint action

¹ Official maps of the area are available as links in footnotes below.

² <https://www.tnp.si/en/>.

³ <https://www.parcoprealpigiulie.it/it/>.

⁴ <https://www.europarc.org/transboundary-cooperation/>.

⁵ <https://www.europarc.org/library/europarc-events-and-programmes/european-charter-for-sustainable-tourism/>.

(formal agreement between the PNPG and Slovenian hunting reserves, also called “hunting families”) concerned the protection of the Alpine ibex that was reintroduced in an area of the PNPG bordering Slovenia (the Canin area). Due to legislative differences in the two countries, the ibex is protected in Italy but can be hunted in Slovenia. Therefore, thanks to the intermediation of the TNP, an agreement was concluded between the PNPG and Slovenian hunting families to limit hunting ibexes and ensuring the protection of the animals reintroduced on the Italian side.

The cooperation process evolved in the framework of the EUROPARC Federation:⁶ In 2009, EUROPARC proclaimed the establishment of the Julian Alps Transboundary Ecoregion, and, in 2016, awarded this Transboundary Ecoregion with the ECTS, making it the first transboundary protected area in Europe to receive this recognition. The broader framework of the Transboundary Ecoregion reflects the commitment to balancing conservation goals with sustainable development and fostering cooperation across the Slovenian-Italian border. The ECTS, which certifies sustainable tourism practices, was confirmed in 2020 and will soon undergo a re-evaluation. In November 2024, the parks met with their stakeholders in the context of the ECST Annual Forum and, on this occasion, presented actions included in the new Action Plan 2025-2029. In addition to the EUROPARC framework, in 2014, the Alpine Convention recognized the area of the TNP and PNPG as a transboundary pilot region for ecological connectivity.⁷

The cooperation among the parks was also formalized through an agreement of the managing units of the TNP and the PNPG, concluded in Trenta (SI) in 2018, so just before the Italian Biosphere Reserve was recognized. In this agreement, the two parks commit themselves to cooperate in the field of biodiversity protection, including the monitoring of species, the exchange of data, education projects, etc. The agreement further establishes that the two parks should cooperate being guided by their 5-year management plans.⁸

The two parks form currently the ecological and administrative foundation of the Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve. In addition to the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, two national Biosphere Reserves that are part of it cohabit and continue to exist.⁹ They were created before the Transboundary Reserve was recognized, the Slovenian one in 2003 and the Italian one in 2019. Both national reserves are managed by the respective parks of reference, the TNP for the Slovenian Reserve and the PNPG for the Italian Reserve.

The Transboundary Biosphere Reserve¹⁰ itself extends beyond the national Biosphere Reserves' boundaries, integrating surrounding foothills, lowlands, and human communities. It must also be noted that the Transboundary Ecoregion (EUROPARC) does not coincide with the Transboundary Reserve but includes the Slovenian National Biosphere Reserve and the territory of the PNPG.

⁶ The story of the cooperation has been derived from interviews (especially [Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI](#), [Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT](#), [Int_JulianAlps_08_OI](#), [Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT](#), and [Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT](#)), as well as from official documents, see in particular the Candidature of the Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (Italia-Slovenija), available at https://www.tnp.si/media/5290/julianalpstbr_nomination_form_printed_version.pdf. See also: <https://www.parcoprealpigiulie.it/it/principale/territorio/storia#:~:text=Il%20Parco%20naturale%20regionale%20delle,cammino%20durato%20oltre%20due%20decenni.>

⁷

See https://www.alpconv.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Fotos/Banner/Organisation/thematic_working_bodies/Part_01/ecological_network_platform/9_Pilotregionen_e-2.pdf; <https://alparc.org/news/julian-alps-ecoregion-becomes-europe-s-first-transboundary-park-awarded-with-the-european-charter-for-sustainable-tourism-certificate>; <https://www.tnp.si/en/park/area/ecoregion-julian-alps/>; and https://www.alpconv.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Fotos/Banner/Organisation/thematic_working_bodies/Part_01/ecological_network_platform/8_Report_62_P_C_Alpine_Convention_Evaluation_Pilot_Regions_2016.pdf.

⁸ Cooperation agreement signed in Trenta on June 20, 2018, art. 2(2), p. 3.

⁹ https://www.tnp.si/media/5325/cezmejna_brosura_ang2018.pdf

¹⁰ http://www.julianalps-mab.eu/MAP_Proposed%20Julian%20Alps%20Transboundary%20Biosphere%20Reserve.pdf

The Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve,¹¹ designated under UNESCO's MAB program, is a transboundary initiative that reflects the shared commitment of both Italy and Slovenia and the respective national Biosphere Reserves to pursue three main functions, namely conservation, development, and logistic support (research, monitoring, and education).¹² The MAB reserve concept in the Julian Alps began with the establishment of the Slovenian Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve in 2003, which covers most of the TNP. This recognition highlighted the area's ecological and cultural significance and provided a framework for sustainable management. In 2019, the Italian Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve was formally recognized by UNESCO. Its creation marked a step toward closer collaboration, as it adopted the name Julian Alps to signal the intention to merge with the Slovenian reserve under a transboundary framework.

The Transboundary Biosphere Reserve was formalized through a process that included extensive stakeholder engagement, beginning in 2021 with a cooperation agreement between the TNP and the PNPG. This collaboration was supported by official agreements signed by the Slovenian and Italian national governments in 2023, signifying a mutual commitment to the MAB program's goals. These agreements aim to align conservation, research, and community engagement initiatives across borders. UNESCO recognition finally came in July 2024. With this recognition, the artificial division between the Italian and Slovenian Julian Alps Biosphere Reserves is overcome, uniting 277,000 hectares under a shared commitment to sustainability.

Picture taken from the candidature document for the recognition of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve

Concerning the governance of this cooperation, in the framework of the ECST the two parks established a Steering Group which includes the Directors and staff from both parks and meets quite regularly (every

¹¹ See <http://www.julianalps-mab.eu/> and <https://www.unesco.org/en/mab/julian-alps-0>.

¹² See <https://www.unesco.org/en/mab/wnbr/about> and UNESCO (2022), *Technical Guidelines for Biosphere Reserves*, available at <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000375692>.

three or four months). The Steering Group is not formally recognized by any agreement but has consolidated through the practice and mentioned into transboundary cooperation documents between the parks; meetings of the Steering Group are formalized by the adoption of minutes. During the meetings the participants usually review the Action Plan for Transboundary Ecoregion Julian Alps by discussing the actions developed since the latest meeting, the challenges faced, and how to proceed further. This modus operandi facilitates monitoring the action plan but does not necessarily provide feedback on the effectiveness of the actions in terms of transboundary biodiversity conservation. In addition, the personnels of the two parks have daily relations via email or phone to exchange information on their joint actions. The Action Plan for Transboundary Ecoregion Julian Alps is also reviewed in a participatory informal format: Every year the two parks organize an Annual Forum, where they invite the main stakeholders in the Julian Alps, to discuss the actions included in the Action Plan, to what extent they have been carried out, and what has to be improved.

In the framework of the recently recognized Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, a more structured governance is foreseen¹³ with the aim of ensuring an effective participation of the most significant territorial stakeholders and an enhanced connection among the two National Biosphere Reserves governance structures. The Transboundary Biosphere Reserve governance structure will be additional to the ones of the National Biosphere Reserves, which remain responsible for projects focusing on local level and regarding only one side of the Julian Alps and maintain relations with the national MAB Biosphere Reserves Networks and all concerned institutions and stakeholders. Instead, the transboundary structure will deal with the cooperative projects between the two sides of the Julian Alps and the involvement of stakeholders from both countries in the fields of ecology, culture, society and economy, as well as the interaction with the World Network of Biosphere Reserves of the MAB Program. Furthermore, the transboundary governance is responsible for maintaining a relationship with the neighboring Austrian region to further strengthen cooperation in the Julian Alps and with a view to a future expansion of the transboundary biosphere reserve.

The transboundary governance structure consists of a Coordinating Committee, supported by a Permanent Secretariat, and the following consultation and coordination mechanisms: a Young Advisory Board, the ECST Forum, and some thematic Transboundary Cooperation Tables.

The Coordinating Committee should be convened regularly, at least once a year, and be composed of twelve members: one representing the TNP; one representing the PNPG; six selected among the regional/local authorities and/or members of the two national Julian Alps Biosphere Reserves' Boards (three for IT and three for SI); two youth representatives (one from SI and one from the Youth Council of the IT Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve); one representative from a Professional Nature Conservation Institute (SI); and one from the Scientific Board of the Italian Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve. This committee is responsible for defining and developing the Transboundary Reserve Work Plan, which focuses on topics and issues of common interests, and details the common objectives and measures relating to nature conservation, cultural diversity, land management, sustainable development, research, monitoring, education, and training. It also deals with realizing joint activities on the aforementioned topics, including enhancing the effectiveness of the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve in line with UNESCO recommendations; promoting the implementation of participatory processes to involve local communities and stakeholders in joint projects and actions; and building on the results achieved with the ECTS in terms of sustainable tourism strategies and actions. The Committee will be chaired by the parks' members based on a two-year rotation principle starting with the TNP. It is also foreseen the creation of a Committee's Permanent Secretariat, which will represent the focal point for local communities and will be composed of three people on each side of the Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (the Director and two employees for each park). The Secretariat mirrors the structure of the aforementioned Steering Committee that currently operates among the parks. The Secretariat will set its own operating

¹³ See section 7 of the Candidature, *supra* note 6.

rules and decision-making process. In the candidature it is established that financial and human resources are mainly provided with the TNP and PNPG's ordinary budget and staff.

The Transboundary Cooperation Tables and the Young Advisory Board should take place in person or online once or twice a year and gather different actors from IT and SI, and aim, *inter alia*, to promote synergies, collaboration, and exchange of good practices in the following sectors or among specific stakeholders: 1) agriculture and forestry, 2) University and research groups, 3) cultural and traditional associations, 4) school and education, and 5) young people. The ECST Annual Forum could be maintained as already established in the framework of the ECST or replaced by a similar arrangement that includes protected-area authorities, national and regional bodies, local municipalities, community representatives, as well as stakeholders from the conservation and tourism sectors.

The effectiveness of the Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve will be evaluated through a periodic review every ten years to monitor the goals and actions identified in the Work Plan. In particular, during the ten-year period, a periodic monitoring of cooperation actions is foreseen every two years to update the status of the actions foreseen and add new ones, if needed. In addition, every five years the effectiveness of the Work Plan is assessed in terms of the general objectives pursued to adapt them, if needed. The final re-evaluation (after ten years) will result in a new Work Plan.

1.1 Selection of interviewees

The selection process of the interviewees followed the stakeholder engagement and desk research phase, during which a broad pool of stakeholders was compiled. After meeting with the parks and attending the 2023 Annual Forum in Log pod Mangartom (Slovenia), new contacts were acquired, and the pool of stakeholders was narrowed down. Snowballing was also applied with the parks acting as gatekeepers and facilitating access to stakeholders and giving new contacts. The final selection was done with the aim of including the most representative actors of the main institutions/sectors active in the cooperation or affected by/contributing to it. Additionally, some interviewees also pointed out to new contacts, normally within their organizations, when they were not experts on a given topic. Regional actors not based locally, like EUROPARC and the Alpine Convention Secretariat, were also included given that they have an influence on cooperation in our case study. Assuring a balance between the two countries was also a factor that was present in the selection process. The following table includes additional information such as the pseudonymization code, which contains reference to the case study (Julian Alps), the number of the interview (e.g., 01), the abbreviation of the interviewee's category (e.g., Park Management, PM), and the country in which the interviewee operates whenever relevant (SI or IT). The table below also specifies the date of the interview and the categories of stakeholder to contextualize the responses. As a final note, it is important to mention that, although we repeatedly tried to involve Slovenian municipalities, we got no responses to our requests, even when an intermediary working closely with one Slovenian municipality offered to look for potential interviewees in that municipality.

Interview code:	Date:	Category of stakeholder
Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI	24.04.2024	Park Management (PM)
Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT	24.04.2024	PM
Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT	24.04.2024	PM
Int_JulianAlps_04_IO	30.05.2024	International Organization (IO)
Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT	20.06.2024	National Authority (NA)
Int_JulianAlps_06_IO	04.07.2024	IO
Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT	18.07.2024	Regional Authority (RA)

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI	01.08.2024	Other Interest Groups (OI)
Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI	07.08.2024	PM
Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT	13.08.2024	Youth (Y)
Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT	19.08.2024	Local Authority (LA)
Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI	28.08.2024	NA
Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI	29.08.2024	NA
Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI	03.09.2024	NA
Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT	05.09.2024	Economic Sector (ES)
Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT	12.09.2024	Civil Society (CS), OI
Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI	18.09.2024	OI
Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI	20.09.2024	ES, Y
Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI	26.09.2024	ES
Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI	26.09.2024	NA
Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT	03.10.2024	PM, LA
Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT	22.11.2024	CS

1.2 List of abbreviations and report language

Besides the abbreviations in the table above, this report employs several additional abbreviations, which are detailed in the table below. The terminology utilized aligns with the conventions of the discipline and broader research practices. Interview identifiers and stakeholder categories adhere to the project methodology agreed by all partners. Where remarks from interviewees require contextualization or factual clarification, explanatory comments have been provided in angle brackets: [..., ed]. Also, when terms in Italian were difficult to translate, the original Italian word has been kept close to the translation between round parentheses and in italics: e.g. municipal councilor (*assessore*). For the sake of clarity, additional information can be found in footnotes and the reference section. Finally, to ensure a full degree of pseudonymization, interviewees are never referred to with gender specific personal pronouns, such as he/she or his/her. In contrast, personal pronouns are always used in the plural neutral form – they, their or them – although interviews are in most cases individual.

ABB	Alpine Biodiversity Board (of the Alpine Convention)
ARPA	<i>Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione dell'Ambiente</i> /regional agency for environmental protection (for Region FVG)
AT	Austria
CBC	Cross-Border Cooperation
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CIA	<i>Confederazione Italiana Agricoltori</i> / Italian Farmers' Association

CIPRA	<i>Commissione internazionale per la protezione delle Alpi</i> /International Commission for the Protection of the Alps
CLLD	Community Led Local Development
ECST	European Charter of Sustainable Tourism
EGTC	European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EU	European Union
EUSALP	EU Strategy for the Alpine Region
FVG	Friuli Venezia-Giulia (an Italian region)
GAL	<i>Gruppi di azione locale</i> / Local Action Groups
INSIEL	<i>Informatica per il sistema degli enti locali</i> /Regional Informatics Agency of FVG
IPA	Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance
ISPRA	Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale – Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
IT	Italy
IUCN WCPA	International Union for the Conservation of Nature – World Commission on Protected Areas
MAB	Man and Biosphere
MASE	<i>Ministero dell’Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica</i> – Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security
MEP	Member of European Parliament
NRRP	National Recovery and Resilience Plan, also known in Italian as PNRR
PNPG	Parco Naturale Prealpi Giulie
RDPs	Rural Development Programs
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SI	Slovenia

TNP	Triglav National Park
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
YC	Youth Council
WISO	Large Carnivores, Wild Ungulates and Society Working Group (of the Alpine Convention)

2 Summary of the interviews

2.1 General information on experiences of the interviewees with transboundary biodiversity conservation efforts and the cooperative setting in which they are placed

How was the interaction between the relevant actors described by the different interviewees?

In addition to responding to the question above, this section describes in which capacity the interviewees are responding to the questions. This is specified in order to contextualize their responses when it comes to both the actors they are mainly interacting with and the rest of the responses given.

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: The main transboundary connections of the Triglav National Park (TNP) are with the staff of the Parco Naturale Prealpi Giulie (PNPG), but not with other institutions in Italy. This kind of contacts are curated by other colleagues of the interviewee, especially within the framework of cooperation projects. Cooperation is ongoing also with Austrian parks, such as the Dobratsch and Karawanken parks in Austria, the Mercantour park in France, the Snowdonian National Park in Wales, the Berchtesgaden and the Nature Park Taunus in Germany, the American Great Lake National Park in the US, and the Valley of Flowers in India. With some of these parks they have signed partnerships for the exchange of best practices (PNPG, Mercantour, Berchtesgaden), with others they cooperate in projects or have sporadic contacts. Within Slovenia, the TNP cooperates with other Slovenian parks within the framework of an association of Slovenian parks, in the framework of which the directors of parks meet once in a while. The cooperation with international partners is weaker than that with PNPG.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The interactions described are of 4 types: (1) those within large networks of parks, such as Alparc (Alpine arc), EUROPARC (European parks, especially in the sub-networks of the program Transboundary Parks and the European Charter of Sustainable Tourism - ECST), and Federparchi (Italian parks); (2) those, the closest and the only truly transboundary ones, between the PNPG and the TNP within the Steering Group and through daily, even more informal, communications (see below section 2.2); (3) with local stakeholders mostly on the Italian side of the border; and (4) with other European parks (usually members of the association mentioned under (1)), such as Nockberge, Weissenseen, and Dobratsch (AT), typically in the context of EU-funded projects but also bilaterally. The interviewee highlighted that interactions mostly occur at the borders between Italy, Slovenia, and Austria.

The medium to long-term goal in this sense is to create a unified UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve that includes also Austrian partners. It is important to consider that transboundary cooperation under (2) and (4) ranges from protection of some species, ecological connectivity, education to sustainability, research, exchange of best practices, to infrastructural developments (ex. creation of the visitor center in Trenta that is now the main seat of the Transboundary Ecoregion Julian Alps).

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: The interviewee interacts with several actors at different levels: locally, with the administrators [of the municipalities, ed.] located in the territory of the PNPG, the park staff and actors working within the area, such as, regional forestry corps that oversee patrolling activities and participate to monitoring; freelancers in different sectors (from territorial planning and construction professionals to the researchers in faunistic and floristic studies); nature guides, mountain and mid-mountain guides, and other categories of guides; third sector entities: environmental, agricultural and other associations located in municipalities both within the park area and outside, with a national or supranational dimension, and collaborating with the PNPG (such as Legambiente and the Italian Farmers' Association - CIA). Important interactions exist with schools (both local ones and those coming to visit the PNPG), university and the academic/research sector. Internationally, interactions are created for institutional reasons (i.e. EUROPARC and Alparc networks) and through projects. The national Biosphere Reserve, which is coordinated by the PNPG, also led to new relations, for instance with UNESCO as well as with local associations that are also well connected internationally: this is the case of the local branch connected to the European Green Belt Association. Therefore, interactions are varied and can range from the Italian and Slovenian Environmental Ministries to citizens who need to cut trees in the forest or receive subsidies for lawn mowing or pasture. FVG regional authorities are also interlocutors due to their faunistic competences. On the Region FVG, the interviewee said that they need to interact with the TNP to address transboundary conservation issues that go beyond the territory of the PNPG, but that this interaction happens in practice through the intermediation of the PNPG. In the framework of the transboundary cooperation of the two national MAB Reserves, the main actors are the two parks, the PNPG and the TNP, which are the managing authorities of the MAB Reserves.

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: In their personal and professional capacity, the interviewee interacts with directors and staff of protected areas, and other biodiversity experts.

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: The interviewee said that one of the main actors for the MASE is the Alpine Convention. The interviewee mentioned the fact that the Protocol on Nature Protection of the Alpine Convention contains a provision where States endeavor to create national networks, in order to join international networks. Alparc is one of these networks, an important actor for transboundary cooperation in the area. Among the Italian networks of which PNPG is part since its creation in 2013-2014, the interviewee mentions an Italian network of Alpine protected areas¹⁴. Within the Alpine Convention, the Alpine Biodiversity Board (ABB)¹⁵ is an important actor that sets an overarching framework of cooperation to promote the harmonization of Alpine biodiversity monitoring. The work of the ABB also aims to highlight the importance of the specificity of Alpine biodiversity also in the national strategy on biodiversity. The ABB is advocating for the importance and specificity of Alpine biodiversity also at the level of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). The ABB, and therefore also the interviewee within it, is interacting with other working groups of the Alpine Convention, such as the Large Carnivores, Wild Ungulates and Society Working Group (WISO) that deals with large carnivores, and the group on Spatial Planning. The Italian MASE is furthermore involved in cooperation projects that aim to promote ecological

¹⁴ It might be the SAPA network (<https://www.federparchi.it/pagina.php?id=38#:~:text=Cos%27A8%20la%20Rete%20SAPA,%2C%20e%2019%20Enti%20parco>), but we are still verifying with the interviewee.

¹⁵ Its current task is mainly to elaborate an Action Plan on Alpine Biodiversity and its implementing guidelines.

corridors and green bridges. The MASE also works on strengthening transboundary cooperation for the harmonization of monitoring data, that are instrumental for identifying areas where to prioritize restoration measures. These activities need to be carried out not only in the territory of Italian parks, like PNPG, but also in transboundary border areas, like that of the TNP or the Mont Blanc area. Cooperation is also ongoing with the Carpathian Convention and the CBD Secretariat. At the local level, the Ministry collaborates with regional administrations. The Italian Ministry also cooperated with the Slovenian counterpart for the presentation of MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve candidature, which was presented to UNESCO in September 2023. The Ministry has an internal technical committee to evaluate potential candidatures.

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: The interviewee is not directly involved with territorial actors in the Julian Alps. Interactions are mainly with national representatives and technical experts involved in the ABB and the WISO group as well as observers of the Alpine Convention (scientific institutes, environmental associations like CIPRA, Alparc, etc.).

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: The interviewee interacts with the Director and the President of the PNPG on a daily/weekly basis depending on the needs; there is a close collaboration and direct communication. The two Regional Parks in FVG are operating entities (*ente strumentale*) of the Region by Regional Law 42/96 on protected areas, they are autonomous from an operational point of view but remain within the regional legal framework that regulates their operativity. There is no formal interaction with the TNP, but the relations are maintained through the PNPG. Otherwise, since the TNP is a national park, formally and in line with administrative hierarchies, the Italian MASE should be involved to speak with Lubiana. However, since the parks' staff work together and know each other well, it is easier for the Region FVG to speak with the TNP President or park personnel directly at the operational level in an informal way. The projects/activities with the TNP are not managed by the FVG Region directly, but via the PNPG.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: While the interviewees' work predominantly involves Slovenian stakeholders, collaboration with Italian counterparts is common, especially through EU-funded projects and frameworks like the Alpine Convention. The TNP also actively participates in international networks, such as EUROPARC and Alparc, and has sister park agreements worldwide. These collaborations foster knowledge exchange and shared initiatives but often rely on limited resources and personal networks for continuity.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: The interviewee explains interactions of the Youth Council (YC) of the PNPG, which is composed of about 28 young people under 30s, has its own budget, and is a consultative body of the PNPG. One representative of the YC sits in the park's Management Board, in pursuance of the regional Law on regional parks, amended recently to allow for that. Lately the collaboration with PNPG is limited to environmental education and teaching activities with schools, groups and for summer camps, and the project "Sustainability Paths" (*Sentieri di sostenibilità*): a camp in collaboration between the FVG UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserves of the Julian Alps and Miramare. The interviewee is also active in the EUROPARC Federation, again for a project focusing on youth involvement in protected areas. Further contacts with local and external stakeholders were established due to the role of YC spokesperson: locally, within the Park Management Board, with regional and local administrators, politicians, and technical staff of the FVG Region; at the European level, within the EUROPARC network also during their annual conferences. With some of the actors met, the interviewee has had and still maintains personal and professional relations.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The interviewee interacted and interacts with many actors both for the several roles covered in the PNPG and the direct involvement since the park's beginning, and for the role as local administrator.

Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI: The interviewee was involved in the interview process as an expert of hunting for Slovenia but is not much involved in transboundary cooperation in the area. Hunting regulation is centralized, that is why we found it useful to interview this person. Also, the interviewee was selected because they collaborate with the TNP concerning wildlife management and planning. The role of the national body to which the interviewee belongs is to monitor wildlife and to evaluate damages made by wildlife to other sectors, such as agriculture. This national body and the interviewee work with local hunters. Local hunters were not interviewed for Slovenia. The national body also used to be involved in international projects, for instance for population sampling, but not necessarily in the area of the Julian Alps.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: The interviewee's experience includes working on international agreements such as Ramsar, and they contributed to the application process for the Julian Alps Transboundary UNESCO MAB Reserve. They emphasized that transboundary biodiversity conservation is crucial for ensuring ecological connectivity and ecosystem stability, especially for a small country like Slovenia. Cooperation allows for the exchange of knowledge, research, and good practices among stakeholders while addressing shared challenges such as tourism. The interviewee highlighted the importance of maintaining strong collaborations, particularly at the park level, where protected areas and local actors often lead initiatives.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: The interviewee has extensive involvement in transboundary biodiversity conservation through national and international roles. These include participation in the Alpine Convention and the EU Strategy for the Alpine Region (EUSALP), alongside coordinating with TNP and Alparc. Collaboration between Slovenia and Italy, particularly TNP and PNPG, has a long-standing history of cooperation. This partnership has been recognized in 2014 as a transboundary pilot region for ecological connectivity under the Alpine Convention. Recently, this collaboration was further consolidated with the designation of a UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. The interviewee emphasized that Slovenia's national spatial development strategy also promotes cross-border biodiversity initiatives, framing these as integral to broader green infrastructure development.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: The interviewee's main contacts are with Italian local farmers, especially the Slovenian minority in Italy, because it is the mission of their association. They also have constant direct contacts with the Slovenian ministries, including mainly the Ministry of Agriculture and also the Government Office for Slovenians Abroad, and the Ministry of the Economy. These direct contacts are in addition to those that the Region FVG may have. They have direct contacts also with Slovenian farmers, for example for the organization of local markets and in EU projects (Interreg).

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: The interviewee explains that relations between Italian and Slovenian hunters were established informally, and mostly on a personal friendship basis, by the reserve directed by the interviewee. There was an idea to institutionalize this relationship with mixed commissions that would have had to meet twice a year, but a regional project of 2002-2006¹⁶ to standardize the

¹⁶ This project is explained in the following publication: U. Fattori, A. Rucli, and M. Zanetti (eds) (2010) *Grandi carnivori ed ungulati nell'area confinaria italo-slovena. Stato di conservazione.* Regione Autonoma Friuli Venezia Giulia, 2nd edition, 1-80, available at <https://www.regione.fvg.it/rafv/export/sites/default/RAFVG/ambiente-territorio/tutela-ambiente-gestione-risorse->

transboundary management of wildlife that was behind this idea was never followed up by the FVG Region due to a political change of the responsible regional councilor. There are also some actors that are usually in conflict with local hunters that are regional environmental organizations not based on the territory. These have opposed hunters' projects over the years. Local environmental organizations are different and keener to cooperate. Other relations that emerge from the interview are among hunting reserves and with the park PNPG.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee's association was founded specifically with a transboundary perspective on nature conservation, as ecosystems do not align with human political borders. The interview noted that such cooperation has a long-standing history in the Alps, supported by frameworks like the Alpine Convention. The Slovenian branch works on public interest projects related to nature protection and restoration. Their main focus includes wastewater management, sustainable transport policies, and nature conservation advocacy. While they engage in public consultations and provide expertise, they sometimes feel overlooked or excluded by other stakeholders probably because of their watchdog position, which involves challenging and critiquing the practices of public institutions like the TNP. The interviewee expressed a complex relationship with the TNP, as the organization is alternately a collaborator and a critic. Frustration was expressed with exclusion from critical processes, such as the development of TNP's management plan, which was described as lacking transparency and proactive inclusion of NGOs. The interviewee reported that the organization was not consistently involved in cooperative efforts or decision-making, especially in cross-border settings.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: While transboundary biodiversity conservation was recognized as essential, the interviewee had limited direct involvement with these initiatives. The interviewee emphasized that nature transcends borders and regions like the Julian Alps should be managed as cohesive units. However, there are limited formal connections between Slovenian and Italian farmers, attributed to differing agricultural practices and geographical challenges. Informal or personal relationships were rare, and no cooperation mechanisms were reported by the interviewee.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee recounted challenges in aligning tourism growth with conservation, particularly as the TNP balances its identity as a protected area and a popular tourist destination. Over the past 15 years, collaboration with TNP has improved, with efforts focused on achieving a balance between nature conservation and tourism development. Initiatives such as the Wildflower Festival have been instrumental in fostering a shared understanding of the importance of biodiversity conservation and creating a sense of local pride. While there is collaboration with the nearby PNPG, the interviewee acknowledged that much of this work has been on small-scale projects, with further development needed to deepen cooperation.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The importance of transboundary biodiversity conservation, particularly due to their work in northwestern Slovenia, an area bordering Italy and Austria was emphasized. Past cooperation focused more on Austria than Italy due to the division of responsibilities with the TNP managing cooperation with Italy. However, the establishment of a cross-border biosphere reserve has increased opportunities for collaboration with Italian partners. Cooperation with Austria was described as historically good, involving both governmental and private actors, although challenges arose when stakeholders, particularly landowners, withdrew from projects. The main difference in approaches lies in historical and legislative frameworks of the cooperating countries, particularly the strength of

[naturali/FOGLIA51/allegati/Grandi_Carnivori_ed_ungulati.pdf](#). In addition to bilateral commission, the Regional Informatics Agency of FVG, INSIEL, had elaborated a software to jointly collect data about and monitor the legal killing of fauna (*abbattimento*) across the borders. This software in the interviewee's view is still stored at INSIEL.

landowners' influence in Austria versus Slovenia's centralized decision-making. Common goals, however, include the protection of species and ecosystems transcending borders.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: The interviewee's role entails mediating, listening, and representing the realities, situations, and wills. Interactions are maintained at both the institutional level and community level, with all citizens. The interviewee explained that the population of the area (*Val Canale*) is less than 10,000 inhabitants within the park: Resia counts 917 people, the municipality of Chiusaforte 630, the municipality of Resiutta around 250, and Moggio Udinese about 1500. It is normal to interact with all the people due to the limited numbers of inhabitants and because they are all stakeholders. At the institutional level interactions are very dynamic as well since they continuously increase by opening new collaborations, projects, and new paths that create opportunities for the area.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: The interviewee is part of an environmental association. They said that this association interacts in a transboundary way with the PNPG and the TNP on specific projects. One of these projects was initiated in 2018 and is about the creation of a Transboundary Peace Park to promote both biodiversity conservation and peace. This park project would include the PNPG, the TNP, and the park Dobratsch in Austria, as well as CIPRA Slovenia and another Austrian association based in Klagenfurt. This project has been slowed down by the Covid pandemic and other circumstances. Now, with the reinstalment of the current director of the PNPG, dialogue has been reignited. In the view of the interviewee, the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Reserve is only an intermediate stage that precedes the creation of the Transboundary Peace Park because it was easier to realize. Before 2018, relationships with the PNPG and the TNP were only sporadic and concerned only the local articulations of this association, for example the branches of the Canale Valley. Another example are activities on the monitoring of glaciers in the Julian Alps, which is part of a national program of their association. Education and communication activities were for instance carried out concerning changing glaciers in the Trenta seat of the Transboundary Ecoregion. The objective is to show how biodiversity is also changing due to glacier retreat. As an association, they also carry out other transboundary activities more to the South in the area of Gorizia (IT)/Nova Gorica (SI). They are cooperating with both municipalities, as well as the Slovenian Agency for environmental protection and the regional agency for environmental protection (ARPA FVG) in order to elaborate transboundary indicators to measure environmental quality across borders. Relations with the Slovenian counterparts (Slovenian environmental associations) has to be improved, because the interviewee admitted that they do not have established contacts, although the interviewee mentioned a project in collaboration with CIPRA Slovenia (see above).

Were there any differences or commonalities identifiable, which are worth highlighting to support the analysis later on in the project?

In terms of commonalities, interviewees seem to agree on the fact that the transboundary cooperation on biodiversity protection in the Julian Alps is managed mainly by the PNPG and the TNP. Other types of stakeholders participate ad hoc, within different types of frameworks and with different degrees of involvement.

In terms of differences, there is an evident difference between the parks and the other interviewees concerning how interaction between relevant actors has been described. The collaboration between the PNPG and the TNP is embedded in larger networks of European cooperation among parks, such as Alparc, EUROPARC, and others. This level of larger embeddedness is completely absent for the other types of local stakeholders interviewed, at least from what emerged in the interviews. In more general terms, although cooperation between the PNPG and the TNP is consolidated, direct transboundary contacts between local stakeholders are less well established.

2.2 Information on the institutional and participatory structures of cooperation

How did the interviewees describe the transboundary cooperation mechanism? Did they identify it as a bottom-up or top-down initiative? Were they able to identify the main decision-makers and how was the decision-making process described in general?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: The interviewee said that the parks were responsible for starting the cooperation. The interviewee defines the parks as a middle-level, the State being the upper level. However, they said that the cooperation can be considered to have been started by the upper level, so top-down, if they consider the parks to be the upper level. The cooperation started because ibex management was different in Italy and Slovenia. In this phase, the initiative was taken also by hunters' associations, in particular the hunting association of Bovec. So, in the end cooperation started as a mix of top-down (parks) and bottom-up (hunters). The interviewee explains the initiative of the parks from the fact that the mountainous habitat of the parks does not allow to have villages directly on the border that would be willing to take the initiative to cooperate. After the first phase, cooperation extended from the ibex to the monitoring of the chamois, large carnivores (including hybridization), and the rock ptarmigan. The main way in which the parks and different actors cooperate on these issues is through projects. The protection of some cultural landscapes, like high meadows, is also within the scope of the cooperation as it has evolved over time. When asked explicitly about the role of agriculture, the interviewee said that the balance between the conservation of species like the wolf is a matter of interest for the cooperation. The main decision-makers at the transboundary levels are the parks (the PGNP and the TNP), but the interviewee highlighted that the national level, the Slovenian competent ministries, supports this cooperation. Concerning the decision-making process, the interviewee described the contacts among the parks continuous: they are obliged to meet 4 times a year due to the certifications [ECST and Transboundary Park program, ed.], but they actually meet at least once a month (either in presence or online) and their informal contacts are much more frequent. The interviewee said that cooperation works particularly well thanks to their willingness to cooperate, their personal friendship developed throughout the years, and the fact that rotating directors have always understood the importance of cooperation and supported it. In terms of the decision-making process, the interviewee said that there is no process to formally coordinate decisions between the parks. What they do is usually to inform each other about documents/decisions that are in preparation within each park. Due to the fact that they are separate legal entities, they have to take separate decisions. They bear responsibility for their decisions and the adoption of legal documents only vis-à-vis their government. The only more institutionalized process of cooperation the interviewee mentioned was regarding the elaboration of the UNESCO MAB candidature to become a Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. Cooperation happens on specific tasks and within the framework of specific projects, such as to monitor species or to create a common map. In the context of these specific tasks/projects, they sometimes involve concerned stakeholders or institutions, such as bird watching associations or scientific experts depending on the issue at stake.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The cooperation between the PNPG and the TNP started already in 1996 when the PNPG was created, and it became stronger over time, especially from 2001. This cooperation is certified by EUROPARC within the context of the Transboundary Park program since 2009 and within the context of the ECST since 2016. The Italian UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserve was created in 2019 in view of creating a transboundary reserve. The interviewee described the start of the cooperation as a top-down process initially, where the PNPG and the TNP played a lead role. Municipalities were the first categories of actors that the parks tried to involve in the cooperation. Consultations with the municipalities were built over time, also because representatives of the municipalities or mayors are part of the Park Management Board (*direttivo*) of the park and thus are constantly informed. The year 2009,

when the parks obtained the certification as Transboundary Park, is considered by the interviewee a turning point. Since then, the cooperation was opened to local stakeholders, including associations and small economic operators such as farmers and breeders, also on the request of municipalities. An example of this involvement is the elaboration of the ECST Action Plan that was done by asking relevant stakeholders what they would have liked to see reflected in the plan. As for the decision-makers, the interviewee identified the parks as main decision-makers that steer the cooperation, also in terms of taking the initiative to participate in EU calls for funds. Since they are recognized as the main actor promoting cooperation, they are also contacted by different sets of stakeholders, such as universities, schools, and associations that promote tourism (*Pro Loco*), to prepare projects in areas of common interest. The interviewee also defined municipalities as decision-makers but only in the sense that requests from citizens are directed to them. Concerning the role of the Region Friuli-Venezia Giulia (FVG), the interviewee highlighted that when it comes to the Biosphere Reserve, the MASE interacts only with the park, thus bypassing the region. The region has a role in promoting existing calls and when it comes to the multi-year planning of the EU funding programs, where it involves the PNPG due to its expertise in order to identify the main priorities. The region is also the managing authority of some EU funded programs and is therefore in charge of audit activities.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: The first instance of cooperation was an agreement with hunting reserves in Slovenia thanks to the mediation of the TNP to protect the Alpine ibex, which is protected by law in Italy but can be hunted across the border. Cooperation started as a top-down process, led by the parks and guided by previous relations between Alpine clubs across the borders between Italy and the former Yugoslavia. The Alpine clubs originally joined to discuss common issues or joint rescue operations and put in place a project that involved AT as well.¹⁷ Then, the parks personnel started to exchange as well as people from the parks' territories, but the relations were mostly institutional. Even today, populations across the borders are not so interested in transnational activities, except for specific activities like exchanges among schools or tourism activities. One objective is to broaden the involvement of civil society to enable cooperation among interested actors independently from the parks. Cooperation has been institutionalized in 2018, before the Italian MAB Reserve was recognized, through a cooperation agreement between the parks concluded in Trenta. The interviewee however notes that this cooperation needs to be continuously reinvigorated (*deve essere alimentata*).

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: Regarding the perception that, within the EUROPARC framework, the PNPG and TNP are more focused on the ECST than on the transboundary park recognition, the interviewee highlighted that the cooperation between the PNPG and TNP is exceptional, and their *modus operandi* is so consolidated that they give it for granted. Therefore, they perceive the ECST as something innovative in comparison to the transboundary park program; this is due to the cooperation standard they achieved. However, for other parks, applying the transboundary method can be a strong leverage to improve on many aspects. It was also highlighted that these two EUROPARC recognitions follow different criteria: on the one hand, the ECST does not have fixed standards but can be granted to parks that are working on sustainable tourism at very different levels; on the other hand, the transboundary park program sets certain standards, like the achievement of common objectives, and this could be more demanding and motivating, but the PNPG and the TNP are very advanced in terms of transboundary cooperation. According to the interviewee, the ECST and the transboundary park program are very different, and thus should not compete. In this context, it was mentioned the case of the Alpi Marittime – Mercantour park, which applied for the ECST recognition but not for the transboundary one. It was underlined that within the EUROPARC transboundary program there are less parks involved, but the network (TransParcNet) is

¹⁷ The interviewee said the project was probably called 30 Peaks (*30 Cime*) and those climbing ten peaks in IT, SI and AT would receive a prize.

very active and, according to the interviewee, more interesting than the ECST network. For this reason, the interviewee and the former EUROPARC colleague dealing with the ECST network wanted to enhance the connection between these two programs and networks to provide the parks with a toolbox and give them the chance to select what they needed most.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: The interviewee highlighted that the cooperation approach adopted in the Julian Alps embraces IT, SI, and AT: For instance, there is a constant relation with the Dobratsch Park as well. The vision is to have a unified management of the Julian Alps and thus extend the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve to AT as well. The Interreg IT-AT ensures cooperation within the two countries and there is a project database (*banca progetti*), which could be further enhanced, aimed at ensuring continuity with past projects and maintaining a line of intervention rather than changing strategy. This avoids forgetting past projects and the results achieved therein. This element could be reinforced to ensure continuity in the projects.

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI: The interviewee shared their knowledge on the institutional structure of cooperation planned in the candidature of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. The main novelties of this scheme are the following: 1) the territory of the Italian reserve is much larger than the territory of the PNPG; 2) this implies also the involvement of a broader set of stakeholders; 3) the parks, as managing authorities of the reserve, may set for them broader objectives than conservation.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: The interviewees described transboundary cooperation as primarily bottom-up, initiated at the park level rather than driven by national governments. This approach has led to the development of joint initiatives and a formalized cooperation framework between the TNP and the PNPG. The parks maintain a joint committee [Steering Committee, ed.] that sets an annual agenda for collaboration, ensuring that activities align with common goals. The main participatory mechanisms are Annual Forums that are held yearly, alternating between Slovenia and Italy, and include broad stakeholder participation. However, transboundary cooperation beyond park management remains limited, with legislation and national-level support posing significant challenges.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: On the institutional structure, the interviewee said that the YC has a consultative role within the PNPG, that a member of the YC sits in the Park Management Board since recently (see section 2.1 above), and that they aim to create a YC also for the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. The YC has a consultative role and supports decision-making processes in the PNPG by bringing an innovative and different perspective. After the creation of the Italian Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve, the YC of the PNPG became the YC of the Biosphere Reserve and thus young people from five more municipalities can become YC members. This expansion brought new forces within the YC and a stronger involvement of young people coming from the five additional municipalities located in the Reserve. The YC is very active at territorial level and has been included within the Biosphere Reserve governance system. With the recognition of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve the idea is to create a transboundary YC [IT and SI youth ed.] to be included in the governance system. This objective was already included in the Action Plan for the Transboundary Ecoregion Julian Alps, but in the TNP there is a wide generational gap due to the abandonment of youth dedicated projects: The TNP recently started with activities for children, but a group of young adults is missing. A recent reform in FVG foresees a young representative in the Park Management Board of the regional parks; the youth representative usually belongs to the YC. The interviewee specified that the PNPG staff in contact with the YC are the Director and the officer responsible for environmental education.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The project behind the park was to combine conservation with development, a pair that is reflected in the MAB recognition as well. The idea was to use conservation or the peculiarity of these areas in terms of natural environment to leverage sustainable development at local level and support the creation of new economic activities, but the results achieved were less than what was expected. The area of the PNPG and surrounding is described as an internal area within internal areas, affected by the 1976 earthquake and degradation also in anthropological terms, due to depopulation. There was not so much need for conservation since human activities are very limited, but the PNPG was seen as an opportunity for social improvement (*riscatto*). Actually, the few human activities in the park (shepherd's cottages and pastures) are preserved and supported/enhanced since they contribute to the biodiversity of the area. The PNPG does not border the TNP directly, but with the Slovenian MAB area in the Canin mountain area. The interviewee mentioned that the first project of the PNPG was well supported by local citizens/actors, especially hunters. At the beginning of 2000, the ibex was reintroduced in the Canin (IT side); the ibex can be hunted in SI, but not in IT. Therefore, there was the need to protect the animals reintroduced in IT and an agreement was signed with the so-called Slovenian "hunting families" (hunting associations). This led to the cooperation with the TNP as well. Despite the geopolitical tensions at the beginning of the 90s, the PNPG and the TNP started to talk about nature, which does not respect borders. The interviewee highlighted that there is friendship across the borders, the latter are a political creation, but do not divide people since they all inhabit mountain areas, have similar problems, the same culture, and have similar traditions. All these affinities facilitate cooperation. However, with the approval of the national law on parks, hunters withdrew their support, and this has caused problems since. It was said that hunters were opposing the park project and highlighting all the limitations that it would imply for local actors and economic sectors. This narrative had an impact on some municipalities, which withdrew their interest in the project and whose territories were not included in the PNPG area, which embraces only 6 municipalities. Nevertheless, the more recent establishment of the MAB Reserve attracted again the attention of other municipalities, as the MAB Reserve embraces 11 in total. The transboundary project has evolved throughout the years and has led to the recent creation of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. This transboundary MAB recognition reflects the essence of being as one: The Julian Alps are the mountains that identifies these territories without borders, regardless of being Italian or Slovenian. The PNPG Management Board supported the Transboundary MAB recognition process and, before that, the creation of the national Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve. A crucial step for the creation of the national Reserve was involving more municipalities to increase the area. This process was long and complicated, hunters were also involved by mayors to make sure that they could operate within the MAB area. According to the interviewee, the FVG region had initially disregarded the complexity of this process: It only gave a formal approval to this project by adopting a decision (*delibera*), but no money. The PNPG Management Board and park staff did most of the work for the recognition of the national MAB Reserve, and their real motivation was the successive transboundary objective.

Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI: The interviewee was able to identify hunting as having an important role in the creation of the TNP. Before the park was constituted, the area was a big hunting reserve where also foreign hunters were allowed to hunt. This was a big source of income for the area, especially for the income produced through the selling of ibex trophies and game population. In the 1970s, however the chamois population declined steadily due to an illness. Thus, there was the idea to create the park to preserve endangered species and sustain the local population because guards of the hunting reserves were reconverted into park rangers when the park was created in 1981. Concerning hunting as the main factor triggering transboundary cooperation in the Julian Alps, the interviewee explained that, although legislations are different and difficult to change, in the year 2000 when Italy started protecting the ibex, there was an informal agreement between Italian and Slovenian hunters that the latter would not kill ibex for 20 years. As far as the interviewee knows, this agreement was respected. According to the interviewee, furthermore, in the past there have been contacts between Slovenian hunting families and

Italian hunting reserves.¹⁸ Concerning the participation of their organization in the Steering Group among the parks or in the Annual Forum, the interviewee said they were not the right person to respond to that. Since the interviewee is not directly involved in transboundary cooperation in the Julian Alps, as they explicitly admitted, they described more general mechanisms of transboundary cooperation, such as the participation in international projects or specific funds for pilot projects on small areas to preserve biodiversity. These pilots may then be transferred to wider areas.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: Slovenian national authorities (competent ministry) support transboundary cooperation primarily through global and regional conventions, European projects, and bilateral collaborations with neighboring countries. For example, initiatives such as LIFE and cohesion projects facilitate joint conservation and restoration efforts. The interviewee noted that while the ministry plays a supporting role, much of the actual cooperation is implemented at the park level, particularly by the TNP and its Italian counterpart, the PNPG. These parks have a history of strong collaboration, which has been formalized and further supported through mechanisms like the UNESCO MAB Reserve framework. Despite this, the interviewee acknowledged that differing national legislations pose significant challenges to effective transboundary cooperation. For instance, the legal frameworks governing biodiversity differ between Slovenia and Italy, complicating shared management efforts.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: The interviewee did not discuss this point explicitly but made clear that decisions are perceived by farmers as top-down.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: Regarding the origin of the PNPG, this interviewee said that the procedure to create this park was initiated already in the 1970s by hunters, because in 4 of the 6 municipalities that constitute the park, municipal councilors (*assessori*) were also directors of hunting reserves at that time. The interviewee described this as a paradox since afterwards hunters were limited a lot by the park [after the adoption of the regional law of 1996 and currently in force that institutionalized the PNPG, ed.] and in some phases excluded. Originally the park was conceived as bigger (30,000 hectares) than it is now (9,000) and ungulates' selection hunting (*caccia di selezione degli ungulati*) was allowed by the original law instituting the park [of 1983, ed.], then replaced by the national Law 394/1992 and by the regional law 42/1996, which prohibited hunting in the park area.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee identified government entities as the primary decision-makers in cross-border conservation, particularly for high-level agreements and designations like UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserves. These processes were largely described as bureaucratic and politically influenced. At the operational level, parks like the TNP and PNPG were mentioned as key actors, but their inclusivity and decision-making processes were criticized. Local communities were often brought into the discussion only in a superficial way, with limited opportunities to influence decisions. Cooperation mechanisms were characterized as top-down primarily led by governments and ministries. For example, the designation of the Julian Alps as a UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve was described as being driven by ministries and parks, with little input from other stakeholders.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: The interviewee did not have substantial influence over decision-making and felt the agricultural sector was underrepresented as direct involvement in councils or organizations was sporadic.

¹⁸ The last point is confirmed in **Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT**, although the Italian interviewee emphasized that contacts with Slovenian hunters are only informal in their experience.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee expressed enthusiasm for the recognition of the Julian Alps as a UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, viewing it as an opportunity to strengthen collaborations between Slovenia and Italy. While formal mechanisms exist, such as joint events and initiatives under the Biosphere Reserve framework, the interviewee stressed the need for actionable steps beyond symbolic designations.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The cooperation mechanisms were described as largely project-based rather than systemic. While cross-border conservation is recognized as crucial, government-driven initiatives are limited, and most efforts are initiated through bottom-up project proposals. Decision-making was described as fragmented, with the TNP being a central actor and the Institute for Nature Conservation serving a supporting role. The key decision-makers include national parks, local communities, and landowners. The state-level ministries were described as under-involved, with their role mostly limited to funding. Coordination between ministries, particularly in tourism and nature protection, was described as insufficient.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: According to the interviewee, the cooperation process was guided by the PNPG and the TNP. The perception of this actor is that people of the area lived other dynamics linked to the Second World War and the Iron Curtain. Being a border region for FVG meant a stronger presence of the State, the presence of defense units, infrastructures, custom controls, etc. Then after 1989 with the fall of the Berlin wall – the PNPG was created in '96 - the FVG Region had to reinvent itself as regard to the border component, and this process is still undergoing. The depopulation trend is also linked to the withdrawal of the central State presence in these areas, a consequent decrease in economic activities and primary services,¹⁹ as well as to the lack of a new long-term vision and actions at national level. So, territorial actors had more basic needs [than cooperation ed.]: they had to reinvent their future. The PNPG and the TNP guided cooperation and had a long-term vision supported at technical and political levels, also within the parks. The Transboundary MAB Reserve recognition demonstrates the value of this long-term project.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: Concerning the question of who are the main decision-makers in the Julian Alps, the interviewee responded that the PNPG and the TNP have different structures due to the different institutional frameworks in place [therefore, implicitly the interviewee recognized the parks as the main decision-makers, ed.]. The interviewee also mentioned the Management Board of the PNPG within which environmental associations are allowed to participate. They also mentioned municipalities as important in the context of the PNPG, which was defined a “vast area project” (*progetto di area vasta*) [that by definition includes municipalities, ed.].

Were there any differences or commonalities identifiable between the different interviewees?

Regarding commonalities, interviewees agree that the cooperation was and is still driven by the parks. A partial difference is expressed by **Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI**, which sees the TNP as the long arm of ministerial decisions. Regarding major differences, the role of municipalities is very different on the Italian and Slovenian sides. Italian municipalities had a stronger role than the Slovenian counterparts alongside with the PNPG both prior to and at the time when the cooperation with the TNP was initiated, also

¹⁹ In the interview it was specified that, being a border region between Western and Eastern Europe, in FVG there were national army, customs, etc. With the dismantlement of the Berlin and the enlargement process, State presence was not needed anymore and a part of population left, with spill over effects in terms of economic activities and services.

because representatives of local municipalities were also part of other associations (for instance some municipal decision-makers were also hunters). This disparity is confirmed also by **Int_JulianAlps_08_OI**. It is important to note Slovenian local authorities did not accept to be interviewed although we contacted almost all municipalities present in the park. Therefore, their views might be underrepresented in this report.

Did the interviewees identify any mechanisms or tools which support or guide transboundary cooperation in the area? Were they able to give information on how these, if identified, function?

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The main mechanism of cooperation among the PNPG and the TNP is the Steering Group, an informal body made of 2-3 representatives per park including the focal point for external actors (e.g. EUROPARC).²⁰ They meet regularly in presence every 30-45 days. They produce also official minutes of these “formalized” meetings. The existence of this Steering Group is formalized in the sense that it is referred to in the reports submitted to EUROPARC for the certification as Transboundary Park. The parks also communicate informally via phone or email in a continuous way.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: Cooperation is structured in a way that there is a constant exchange and continuous flow of information between the parks’ management structures. The main decisions are taken within a Steering Group, which is composed of the directors of the PNPG and the TNP and one focal point for each park. Additional people can be involved in the meeting when their specific competence is required. There are around 4 meetings a year in which there is a stocktaking of previous activities and a planning of future steps; this enables a continuous monitoring, which is useful for respecting the commitments linked to the ECST and Transboundary Park certifications. This monitoring is done also for the national Biosphere Reserve. If needed for the issue at stake, a meeting between Park Management Boards is called.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: The topic of how transboundary cooperation is structured emerged in relation to the recent recognition of the Julian Alps as a UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. The interviewee said that the rules and structures to effectively co-manage the Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve are not clear yet, also due to the different administrative levels involved across the borders (national in SI and regional in IT). A reflection is ongoing on the most appropriate legal framework to ensure the joint management of the areas. [In the candidature a governance structure is outlined, ed., see section 1]. Relationship with the TNP should be maintained by the Italian Ministry of the Environment (MASE), since the Triglav is a national park. However, these are maintained locally through the intermediation of the PNPG. One of the issues is that the Italian national level is not aware of the deep level of cooperation in the Julian Alps.

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI: The recognition of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve allows not only to give value to existing national projects that have common objectives across borders and that become part of the projects of the Transboundary Reserve, but also to agree on new projects and objectives that are transboundary in character. An Action Plan or a project database (*banca progetti*)²¹ was developed when elaborating the candidature. The UNESCO MAB recognition is also an incentive for stakeholders that were not keen to cooperate to start doing that, because they are attracted by the brand that this recognition represents.

²⁰ This is the manager of the Julian Alps visitor center located in Trenta, SI.

²¹ Probably the Common Work Plan.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: The main tools facilitating cooperation include EU-funded projects, such as LIFE and Interreg, which enable joint conservation and research initiatives. Regular forums and informal communication channels between park employees also play a key role in addressing urgent issues. Despite these efforts, the absence of harmonized legislation and a lack of systemic national support hinder the implementation of broader strategies.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The interviewee stressed the importance of the recognition of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, which entails having a transboundary area where actions are developed jointly, in line with the UNESCO spirit, and to supersede the heritage of war across this border. An important element of the transboundary Julian Alps Reserve is that all the stakeholders operating at local level understood the importance of this objective – seeing the MAB as a comprehensive project not limited to conservation – and approved and supported this project without local tensions. This is an important step within the MAB process: having all local stakeholders onboard.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: Tools such as UNESCO MAB Reserves and European funding programs (e.g., LIFE, cohesion funds) play a significant role in fostering transboundary cooperation. The interviewee highlighted the importance of bottom-up initiatives, with the ministry primarily facilitating dialogue and providing official support for projects. For example, during the application process for the Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve, the ministry coordinated diplomatic communications, ensured compliance with UNESCO procedures, and supported the parks in their efforts.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: Tools supporting transboundary conservation include platforms like Alparc, which connects protected areas and facilitates knowledge exchange. Additional resources come from Alpine Space programs and regional initiatives like EGTCs, which provide frameworks for joint projects. For instance, an EGTC between Gorizia and Nova Gorica focuses on health, transport, and recreational nature conservation. Such mechanisms provide structured opportunities for regional collaboration and funding.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: The UNESCO MAB was identified as a potential tool for fostering cooperation. The interviewee noted, however, that the agricultural sector was minimally consulted in such processes, relying instead on representations through agricultural organizations, which lack funding and personnel to adequately follow the process and involve local farmers.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee mentioned tools like the MAB Reserve designation, which provides a framework for collaboration, and European funding programs such as Alpine Space projects. These tools facilitate joint initiatives in biodiversity conservation, sustainable tourism, and visitor management. However, the interviewee highlighted that much work remains to incorporate tourism more systematically into these projects, as the tourism sector is often underrepresented in biodiversity-related initiatives.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The MAB reserve designation was highlighted as a critical tool for fostering cooperation, as it encompasses areas outside traditional protected zones. European project funding mechanisms, such as Interreg, cooperation with other states such as Norway or Luxembourg, were also crucial tools mentioned. Despite these, the interviewee stressed the need for permanent, systemic funding.

What is the main form of communication utilized within the transboundary cooperation mechanisms according to the interviewees?

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: Communication is continuous. The members of the Steering Group interact daily via phone call, email, whatsapp in addition to meeting and joint projects. There is a continuous flow and exchange among those people, which has also a friendly character due to their long-lasting relations. The strength is that there is a group of people cooperating in the two parks. The other side of the coin is that there might be the risk that cooperation would be weakened once one of this people retires, thus leaving a communication/relational gap.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: The interviewee referred multiple times to the close relations between the Directors and personnel of the two parks and their continuous communication. A reference was made to the permeability of the IT-SI border and the daily relationship between the communities inhabiting the area.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: Communication with Italian counterparts is both formal and informal. Regular interactions occur during forums, joint committee meetings, and through direct contact between park staff. Urgent issues, such as species management, are typically resolved through informal channels like phone calls, demonstrating a strong reliance on personal networks built over years of collaboration.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: There are annual meetings and continuous communication by the PNPG to its own stakeholders also in the context of the ECST Annual Forum. Due to the lack of youth-oriented initiative in the TNP in the last decade, there is no communication with Slovenian young adults. Communication channels exist between the PNPG YC and younger stakeholders (14-15 yrs old) in the TNP and there is the hope that the latter will help create a YC on the SI side. About a decade ago there was a person from the TNP staff dedicated to promoting youth projects and there was a significant alignment between the PNPG, the TNP, and the Bavarian Forest on the involvement of young adults.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: It was highlighted that the TNP has several internal organizations/associations and the PNPG is in contact with all of them. The PNPG keeps the TNP informed of all its initiatives and aims to involve the TNP, for instance in the project proposals presented in the framework of the Italian branch of Alparc. The interviewee said that the relations between Italian and Slovenian municipalities on the border have existed since before the cooperation between the parks and independently. At the same time, other municipalities that are far from the border and within the PNPG area have transboundary relations through to the intermediation of the PNPG. To avoid duplication (operating as municipalities directly as well as through/with the park) these latter municipalities consider themselves within a broad area and operate through the PNPG [thanks to their direct participation to the Park Management Board, ed.], even more now with the MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. Throughout this interview the strong relationship between the staff of the two parks emerged in a clear way. It was also mentioned that the Management Boards of the two parks meet from time to time to evaluate the objectives achieved and what to do. There are also occasions like local fairs that allow local stakeholders to meet.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: Communication between the ministry and the TNP was described as frequent and efficient, with weekly interactions on various topics, not limited to transboundary cooperation. The interviewee also mentioned collaborative meetings with the Italian Ministry and other stakeholders during the MAB Reserve application process. However, much of the communication and collaboration occurs directly at the park level, where actors have strong on-the-ground knowledge.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: Communication occurs through formal networks like the Alpine Convention's secretariat, which supports contracting parties and facilitates continuity across presidencies. Collaborative meetings, workshops, and project-based interactions are also key. However, the interviewee pointed out that coordination often depends on national and regional actors ensuring alignment with broader frameworks like the Alpine Biodiversity Board or EUSALP.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: Communication among hunters is mainly informal and based on personal relationships.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: There was little interaction between Slovenian and Italian farmers, attributed to language barriers, differences in farming practices, and the lack of structured forums for exchange. Communication tended to occur within national boundaries.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: Communication with the TNP occurs on a daily basis, particularly as the tourism office and the park share facilities in the municipality. However, communication with Italian counterparts is less developed, primarily limited to specific projects or events. The interviewee emphasized the importance of ongoing dialogue and joint problem-solving to avoid fragmented approaches.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: Daily interactions between the ministry and national parks were the primary communication mechanism. Coordination with Italian counterparts is emerging but still contingent on specific projects.

What are the main participatory structures identified by the interviewee? Does civil society make use of these structures, and does it deem them sufficient and suitable for transboundary cooperation?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: The interviewee responded that they do not have specific transboundary participatory tools, except when participation was foreseen on or within specific projects. Within the TNP, they do have two main participatory mechanisms. (1) The first participatory body is the Specialist Council, which is made of 9 members, 4 from the TNP and 5 from different institutions (1 for each institution): the Slovenian Academy for the Science, the Institute for Nature Conservation, the Ministry of the Environment, the Institute for Culture and Preservation of Slovenia, and the Biotechnical Faculty of the University of Ljubljana. This body, which is mainly a technical body of specialists, meets at least three times a year before every meeting of the TNP Board to inform the decision-making process. (2) The other participatory body is the Board of the Park, which is made of 21 members: 10 representatives of municipalities, NGOs (e.g. Alpine Association of Slovenia), owners, hunters (Hunters Association of Slovenia), interested members of the public, ministries' representatives (for environment, farming, economics, and culture), and 1 representative of the TNP. To better understand their functioning and roles, the interviewee invited us to read the Triglav National Park Act.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The main participatory instrument is that, within the framework of the ECST, the parks organize, one year in Italy and one year in Slovenia, the Annual Forum, recognized in the Action Plan for the Transboundary Ecoregion Julian Alps. This meeting aims to involve the main stakeholders [mainly in the tourism sector, although youth representatives and other institutions are present as well, ed.] and is meant to present the main activities carried out and to facilitate the exchange of best practices. Participants may express their views about past activities. It is also an opportunity for stakeholders to propose new activities. For the parks, this event is important because it allows them to have a clear vision

of the perceptions of the stakeholders concerning the activities carried out. Participation of relevant stakeholders also occurs during the application process for EU projects.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: The only formal involvement happens through the ECTS Annual Forum. Few people are interested in biodiversity conservation per se, which is the core aspect of cooperation among the parks. Nevertheless, there are various activities in which civil society actors, like nature guides, associations, and folk groups, interact across borders.

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: The interviewee highlighted the importance of participatory processes through which communities of a given territory may influence the priorities of that territory. In other words, participation is to be conceived not only as preceding the realization of public works but more as a general *modus operandi* to take general decisions. For instance, this should happen to establish priorities and measure to realize ecological corridors. The interviewee also referred to conferences of service (*conferenze di servizi*) under articles 14-15 of Law 241/1990 and further amendments, as a good model for participation.

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI: The preparation of the candidature for the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve was done in collaboration with local stakeholders, as an essential part of a good candidature. In agreement with the parks, the interviewee said that their consultancy decided to include in the participatory process in preparation of the candidature only those subjects that were already involved in the parks' activities. This was not meant to exclude some subjects, and doors were not closed to other subjects during the process. However, priority was given to the subjects that were already involved in the projects of the two national Biosphere Reserves, in order to ensure continuity. They did not do any targeted communication campaign to attract new subjects, but only some announcements in local and social media. The actors that were already involved in the cooperation among the parks were the municipalities, which had supported the national Biosphere Reserves in the first place. There was a disparity there, because the Italian municipalities were great supporters of the Italian Biosphere Reserve (also because this extends beyond the territory of the park), while the Slovenian municipalities have delegated every initiative to the TNP (also because the territory of the Reserve coincides with that of the park). The result was that Slovenian municipalities were less prepared to contribute with concrete objectives and planned actions to the development of the candidature. The other subjects involved were tourist operators, as well universities and research centers. Most of the meetings were organized in English, with some exceptions organized with simultaneous translation (4-5 in total, including the meeting with public officers and, if the interviewee remembers correctly also that with farmers). This choice was meant again only to involve people that may continue to engage with one another also after the candidature was prepared and there would be no specific funds dedicated to organizing meetings with simultaneous translation. In practice, however, since some Slovenians knew Italian, some of them offered spontaneously to translate from Italian into Slovenian and vice versa even in meetings officially organized in English. This means that partially (30-40% of any meeting) some meetings were translated. Furthermore, they thought that in the future linguistic barriers might be likely overcome using AI tools. The recognition of this Reserve might incentivize, according to the interviewee's experience, the participation of actors that otherwise would not be willing to be involved (they said this twice in the interview). However, this enthusiasm needs to be cultivated.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: While Annual Forums aim to include a range of stakeholders, including local communities, the interviewee did not provide specific details on the involvement of civil society in decision-making. The park's efforts to engage local stakeholders in sustainable tourism and conservation initiatives were noted, but systemic participatory frameworks remain underdeveloped.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: The interviewee focused on the participation of youth in the PNPG: the initiatives dedicated to younger pupils (Junior Ranger project since 2007 and activities with schools: “At school in the Park” – *A scuola nel parco*), the creation of the YC, and the efforts to involve young people between the ages of 18 and 30. On the latter point, a connection was made with the issue of depopulation in an area characterized by small mountain rural communities: there are difficulties to inhabit these areas, but people who remain have a strong sense of the community and are involved in voluntary work and all local initiatives (local fair, civil protection activities, mowing, etc.). The YC has a spokesperson that is invited to participate in several events [from the local to the international levels, ed.] together with other local and external stakeholders, including EUROPARC annual conferences and the World forum of biosphere areas. In the preparation of the candidature for the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, the PNPG YC participated by proposing youth-focused actions to be included in the Action Plan, including the creation of a Transboundary Biosphere YC. A similar effort was put in place for the candidature of the national Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve by proposing projects dealing with cultural, historical, territorial, and conservation issues (e.g. project on swift boxes (nests) in municipalities affected by the earthquake in 1976 with new buildings that did not replicate old style buildings with holes for nesting). Compared to the PNPG, the Regional Park of Friuli Dolomites (*Parco Regionale Dolomiti Friulane*) lags behind in youth involvement also due to the remoteness of these areas and their depopulation.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The interviewee mentioned that the PNPG is starting to cooperate with AT protected areas like the Nockberge and Dobratsch. In this context, municipalities can operate through GALs, and this is happening in other areas of FVG, close to Gorizia and Trieste

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: The interviewee did not provide specific details on participatory structures involving civil society. However, they mentioned that public awareness efforts are often organized regionally or locally by protected areas. Examples include educational initiatives like Junior Ranger programs, which target young people to enhance their understanding of biodiversity and conservation.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: The interviewee emphasized the importance of engaging local municipalities and communities, particularly in border areas. However, civil society involvement in structured participatory mechanisms was not explicitly detailed. The interviewee suggested that collaboration with local stakeholders should focus on demonstrating how biodiversity conservation can serve as an opportunity for sustainable development, particularly in remote regions.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: The lack of involvement of farmers, in their view, is mainly due to the limited presence of farmers in the territory of the park, although their farmer association has a very good relationship with the Director of the PNPG. Involving entrepreneurs is also very difficult due to the small size of the farms and the busy schedule of these people that run their companies on their own. The interviewee referred to an example of failed participation in the case of the elaboration of the regional landscape plan (*piano paesaggistico regionale*). In their view, municipalities did not raise enough awareness on this instrument. The interviewee also lamented that farmers are only involved in technical tables, so not when policy aims are decided, and politicians are present.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: The interviewee repeated several times that the initial change of the park (see section 2.8 below and above in this section) alienated hunters’ trust in the institutions (especially at the State and regional level). Since then, it is very hard to involve hunters. Concerning the involvement of hunters in PNPG’s projects or in the preparation of the candidature for the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, the interviewee said that hunting reserves’ directors were always informed, but their involvement has been very limited for the past 2 years (with the previous park director). On the MAB Reserve, the interviewee specified that nobody of the hunting sector opposed the project because it does

not influence wildlife management. The interviewee is anyway critical of how the national MAB area has been managed by the PNPG, because in their view this has been done not in collaboration with local inhabitants.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee expressed frustration with top-down approaches, particularly when they fail to include NGOs and local communities. It was noted that such exclusion leads to ineffective implementation or lack of ownership by critical stakeholders. The interviewee criticized the lack of transparency and proactive inclusion of NGOs in critical processes, such as the development of the TNP's management plan or cross-border initiatives. Information about these processes often came indirectly, such as through informal channels, rather than with direct invitations to participate. It was emphasized that NGOs had to actively push to have their voices heard, highlighting a reactive rather than collaborative dynamic.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: Civil society and agricultural actors had limited engagement in participatory structures for cross-border cooperation. The interviewee suggested that while consultation mechanisms exist, their effectiveness depends on the representatives involved and the resources allocated to participation.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee did not detail specific participatory structures involving civil society. However, they highlighted the Wildflower Festival as an example of an initiative that fosters community involvement by raising awareness about biodiversity and its intersection with tourism and agriculture. This annual festival serves as a platform for engaging local residents in conservation discussions, emphasizing the importance of balancing preservation and development.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The interviewee identified local landowners and communities as pivotal stakeholders in Slovenia, as most protected areas are privately owned. These actors were considered by the interviewee as "opinion-makers" whose support is essential for project success. Civil society's involvement is limited, and the existing structures were not explicitly deemed sufficient, underscoring the need for better engagement frameworks.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: The interviewee spoke about the PNPG Management Board and the importance to meet in this context. Thanks to the staff of the park, municipalities and other involve actors can learn about the activities on the ground, including about the international cooperation activities of the park in the context of EUROPARC or Alparc. This exchange is very important for local administrators, to make them aware of the contexts in which they are called to represent their municipalities. The interviewee mentioned also the exchanges with the PNPG YC. It was said that young people are not many, but very motivated, and it is crucial to empower them and give them space to present proposals as well as the opportunities to realize them. According to the interviewee, citizens and local business know about the [national, ed.] Julian Alps Reserve since they heard or read about it, but they do not know the real implications. These actors have more pressing problems linked to depopulation, socio-economic development, etc. Therefore, it is important to develop concrete actions and projects connected to the Biosphere Reserve and transform it into an opportunity for all.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: Participation in the decision-making process of the PNPG has happened mainly in the context of the Management Board (*direttivo*) of the park where representatives of the interviewee's association are involved [please note that the interviewee was not 100% sure that this participation happened in the context of the Management Board, or if it is another body where environmental associations are allowed to participate, ed.]. This participation preceded the development of specific projects started in 2018 and mentioned in section 2.1 (Transboundary Peace Park and monitoring of

glaciers). Concerning their involvement in the preparation of the UNESCO MAB candidature for a Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, the interviewee said they were involved as association and its local branches, and that they contributed to write specific actions included in the Reserve's Action Plan. Examples of these actions include: the promotion of energy communities within the park, activities of environmental education for schools not based in the park's territory that visit the park, a proposal for a river contract (*contratto di fiume*) for the Fella River, and a proposal to create a Transboundary Peace Park [although the interviewee mentioned these activities, these were not found in the candidature document for the recognition of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, ed.]. When asked if their association has a relationship also with municipalities, they said that they do have it, again in the context of the Management Board where municipalities are represented. They also specified that if they had a project in mind, they know they had to lobby municipalities in the Management Board.

2.3 Information on funding sources and human resources

How are transboundary biodiversity conservation activities funded according to the interviewees and were they aware about a flexibility on the allocation of human and financial resources? Did they think that funding is sufficient, and if not, what was seen as the key reason for the insufficiency of funding?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: Concerning funding, activities for transboundary cooperation are funded through the regular budget of the PNPG and the TNP. The amount is determined every year in the Annual Plan of the park. Human resources are the parks' staff, depending on their specific competences. Regarding specific cooperation activities, funds mainly come from ad-hoc European projects. There are no national funds for transboundary cooperation. The interviewee expressed the view that, although more funds would be welcomed, this would need to be accompanied by more manpower, which usually can be temporarily expanded when projects are funded.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The interviewee said that the transboundary cooperation on biodiversity protection was born thanks to the EU funding programs that are the main funding sources for cooperation in the area: Interreg and Alpine Space programs to fund bi- or multi-lateral projects. The building of the Julian Alps visitor center in Slovenia is an example of that. Other related source of funding are the CCLD (Community Led Local Development)²² projects, especially developed through the GAL, local action groups. CCLD are smaller projects, in terms of partners and available funding [this mechanism is explained better in **Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT** below, ed.]. Specific projects may fund monitoring and action on specific habitats (ex. glaciers) and/or specific species (ex. ibex, ptarmigan - *pernice bianca*). Some projects instead fund infrastructural development (ex. building of the visitor center or info points). Cooperation activities are also funded through the park's own budget, especially to fund ordinary administration, for instance the organization of the Annual Forum or ordinary exchange activities. EU funds instead are used more to do investments. In the last 2 years, limited funds (20,000-30,000 euros) have been also granted by the Region FVG to the PNPG, as managing authority of the Biosphere Reserve, to support cooperation. Recently there has been a ministerial call directed to Biosphere Reserves and related municipalities to abate CO₂ emissions (2023 call) and to promote environmental education in schools. Therefore, there are also some specific national funds, but these are not meant to finance transboundary cooperation because national funds have a national scope, do not foresee the possibility to fund additional partners, and do not have a transboundary vision [plus, they are not specific on biodiversity, ed.]. In practice, however activities funded through these funds may have a transboundary effect: ex. the creation of facilities for electric bikes in an area where bike lanes cross the borders to Austria and Slovenia. Although the

²² See <https://interreg.net/it/progetti-clld-interreg-it-at/>.

transboundary vision is missing in national funds, the interviewee said that the PNPG always tries to include it in what they do. Concerning the question of whether funds are sufficient, the interviewee said that they are proportionate to their current objectives. With the funds available, they manage to cover about 50-60% of the activities planned in the Action Plan [for Transboundary Ecoregion Julian Alps, ed.]. Therefore, they are constantly in search for additional funds to close this gap. However, if they had more funds, the other side of coin would be the lack of sufficient human resources. That is why in new projects they are also asking for funds that would cover fixed-term positions.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: Throughout the years transboundary conservation activities have been financed mainly through Interreg projects. A small quota for transboundary conservation activities is taken from the budgets of the parks. Some resources come from two CLLD linked to the Interreg Italy-Austria. In Interreg Cross-Border Cooperation (CBC) programs, CLLDs are created to transfer the management of some financial resources to local entities, such as the GALs, that grant funds to non-traditional beneficiaries [school, churches, local associations, ed.] to finance small projects responding to territorial transboundary needs. Two CLLDs cover the FVG mountain (especially in the Carnic part: Canal del ferro, Val Canale and the Hermagor region across the AT border). The objective of a CLLD is to fund bottom-up projects. So, part of the IT-AT Interreg is transferred to small entities, like the GALs, that develop – within the wider IT-AT Interreg framework – their territorial strategy. Based on it, they publish calls, and local entities can submit project proposals that have a transboundary value; therefore, there must be at least an Italian and an Austrian partner. There are small projects from 3,000 to 50,000 euros and medium-size projects from 50,001 to 200,000 euros. The aim is involving potential beneficiaries that have difficulties in applying for or are not interested in bigger projects with complex partnerships and complex management. This experience IT-AT has been proposed within the IT-SI Interreg involving GALs operating in the border, but SI opposed this initiative since it prefers promoting small projects that are managed by central authorities and not locally. The human resources involved are those of the parks, but in ECTS projects, other actors can intervene too (Pro loco, cultural associations, etc.).

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: On financial resources available for transboundary biodiversity conservation, the interviewee mentioned that some networks, like EUROPARC, aim to gather an official recognition by donors of their awards, for instance the ECST, to increase opportunities to obtain financial resources as well. For instance, in Spain the ECST is officially recognized by the Ministry of the Environment, and thus parks are interested in gaining such a recognition, since there is the ministerial validation that is additional to the one of EUROPARC. In terms of available resources Interreg programs are mentioned as the primary source to fund transboundary cooperation in Europe, together with HORIZON, LIFE but for cooperation with non-EU countries, there might be difficulties for Norway, Switzerland, etc. to access these funds. In the case of Africa and other continents, there is the development cooperation component with donors (like national cooperation agencies and international organizations), the NEAR for South-Mediterranean, Balkan and East European countries, and other programs for IPA (Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance) countries. Even if there are no specific funds for transboundary biodiversity cooperation, there are financial opportunities within broader frameworks. The latest EU biodiversity strategy deals with transboundary cooperation, maybe this element can strengthen the availability of financial resources. Single protected areas or transboundary parks benefitted from financial support of private donors, banks, foundations, and local funds; for instance, the TransParkNet meeting organized in the Ossola Park, in Italy and bordering Switzerland, was funded by the Cariplo Foundation. In IT, a cooperation project was sponsored with revenues from the Italian annual income tax return (*otto per mille*) donated by taxpayers to the Waldensian Church. Moreover, if cooperation focuses on a specific habitat or species, there may be additional funds, as in the case of cooperation on transboundary basins; here, the transboundary element catalyzes cooperation.

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: There are national funds awarded by the MASE that are directed to national protected areas. There are also more limited regional funds for regional protected areas. When it comes to EU funds, these are the prevalent source of funding for transboundary biodiversity cooperation. In this respect, however, the interviewee has estimated that, notwithstanding the fact the funds at disposal are a lot, only 10% of the funds available has been used for projects focused on biodiversity. According to this interviewee, there is an inner difficulty of preparing projects on biodiversity protection because of the complexity of the topic: Understanding what biodiversity and species are is not straightforward. The interviewee also framed ecosystem services as a form of self-sufficiency or self-funding, because the services provided by the ecosystems somehow are a form of compensation and remuneration for local communities.

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: The interviewee mentioned the Interreg Alpine Space Programme as the main source of funding for transboundary conservation projects pursuing Alpine Convention objectives. The Convention itself does not have internal funding for these projects and relies on the contribution of contracting parties to organize meetings and for the mandate of thematic working groups. It was suggested national funds should be used to guarantee transboundary biodiversity protection on a long-term prospect. Contracting parties should ensure such funds based on the obligations contained in the Alpine Convention.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: Since the PNPG is a regional operating entity, it is financed by the FVG Region. There can also be additional funds for specific projects. Moreover, the FVG Region is transferring the direct management of Natura 2000 sites located in the protected areas to the Parks, which implies additional funds to ensure this management. A dedicated budget line (*capitolo di finanziamento*) was created in the regional budget for the management of the Biosphere Reserve and used to develop the application for the recognition of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. These funds and the transfer of management competence to the PNPG over the Biosphere Reserve have increased the role of the PNPG and its recognition outside the protected area. With the recent recognition of the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, the financial resources might be reorganized; for sure there are specific funds coming from the Dolomiti UNESCO Foundation for the management and promotion of UNESCO sites. At regional level there is the will to guarantee appropriate resources to the two regional parks and ensure their full operativity and pursue all the objectives, including those connected to the management of Natura 2000 sites. In addition, regional parks are invited to apply for EU funds to develop transboundary projects, adopt a dynamic management approach, and open to international relations. The Region FVG chose not to participate in Interreg calls and leaves this opportunity to the regional parks; instead, the Region focuses on LIFE projects. Following the 2015 infringement procedure against Italy for the inadequate approach in the identification of conservation objectives in line with the Habitat and Birds Directives, the MASE is providing funds for environmental restoration: FVG received 300,000 euros for that. These funds cannot be used for monitoring purposes, but given the surplus generated by the ministerial funds, the FVG is using regional funds for supporting monitoring. A consequent issue is getting reorganized within the regional administration to spend appropriately all these resources.

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI: Actors that are UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserves are usually recognized as suitable subjects to become recipients of other funds: they get a higher score just because of their involvement in Biosphere Reserves. For instance, there are (Italian) governmental funds reserved to schools and municipalities and parks that are part of either UNESCO Biosphere Reserves or UNESCO (natural) heritage sites. Funds for schools are aimed at education to sustainability, while funds for municipalities and parks are aimed at energy efficiency. The latter was previously part of a strategy called “Parks for the climate” (*parchi per il clima*), where only national parks were beneficiaries. Now the beneficiaries of these funds are only Biosphere Reserves and not parks, so for instance the National Park of Stelvio is not entitled anymore to use these funds, while the PNPG is (and it used not to be because it is a regional park). There

are also other NRRP (National Recovery and Resilience Plan) funds, like the call “Villages” (*bando borghi*) and others, where if the project concerned a Biosphere Reserve, it would score more, so funding would be more probable. For the funds “pilot areas” directed to internal areas, although the Italian Ministry of the Interior had no official criteria to make Biosphere Reserves score more, these were usually privileged in the awarding of funds. At EU level, instead, there are no funds specifically directed to Biosphere Reserves, although, in the interviewee’s view, unofficially they might be evaluated better than other candidates when projects are of the same (good) level.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: Funding for transboundary conservation relies heavily on EU projects, as national legislation prevents public funds from being used for international cooperation. This dependence creates challenges in sustaining long-term initiatives, as activities often cease when project funding ends. Efforts to establish joint budgets for specific actions, such as shared offices or personnel, have been limited by legal and financial constraints. The interviewees acknowledged that while project funding provides a vital start, finding alternative sources to continue activities is often difficult.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: Youth activities within the PNPG are funded with internal resources, which are regional funds [from FVG, ed.]. Therefore, the PNPG funds the Junior Ranger initiative, the YC, which has an assigned annual budget that can be spent for activities decided by the YC upon approval of the park. Besides that, there are specific projects funded with external sources, like “Youth at the top” promoted by Alparc and funded by a German ministry [the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection and the Principality of Monaco, ed.]. Thanks to the involvement in EU funded projects and EU initiatives, YC representatives can directly participate in various events, travel across Europe to discover, and learn about different realities. The interviewee mentioned the conspicuous financial resources available for grassland restoration, which is a challenge in the PNPG, but the difficulty to use them due to excessive land fragmentation.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The issue of funding emerged in connection with the process for attaining the UNESCO MAB recognition. First, it was underlined that the efforts of the PNPG Management Board and staff in terms of financial and human resources to promote this process and make local stakeholders aware and onboard. Second, the interviewee highlighted the opportunities in terms of financial resources for municipalities in the MAB area since they can access additional funds, for instance those provided by the IT Ministry of Environment and Energy Security (MASE). It was said that local administrators are very keen on new financial opportunities, which can help solve local problems. This is also connected to the re-election dynamics and the need to provide results to citizens within the mandate (5 years). The funds provided by the Ministry have to be used for measures that ensure CO₂ reduction, including conservation activities that ensure this objective: for example, measures for conserving pastures and areas that mitigate CO₂ emissions. Therefore, environmental protection must be ensured and guide the development measures proposed and realized.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: Funding for transboundary biodiversity conservation largely relies on European projects such as LIFE and other mechanisms like cohesion funds. National funding is minimal and often restricted by legislation to activities within Slovenia. While some attempts have been made to establish shared funding mechanisms for cross-border initiatives, most projects depend on external financing. The interviewee stressed the importance of well-prepared proposals to access EU funding effectively.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: The Alpine Convention itself does not provide direct funding for projects but relies on member states’ contributions and voluntary funding for specific initiatives. Larger projects often depend on programs like Alpine Space or external contributions from states like Germany. For instance,

the AlpsLife project,²³ focused on biodiversity monitoring, integrates existing practices with international funding. Resources for working groups also depend on the financial and human capacity of lead countries or ministries. The interviewee highlighted funding challenges, particularly the lack of permanent financial resources to support long-term initiatives. This gap limits the scope of transboundary biodiversity conservation efforts, placing reliance on intermittent project-based funding.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: The FVG Region awards some EU funds (within the CAP) for farmers that commit to maintain pastures through mowing activities (*sfalcio*). However, these funds are not very attractive (see section 2.4 on challenges below). As farmers they have been involved also in some Interreg projects that fund transboundary cooperation for the preservation of some plant varieties (ex. chestnuts trees and seeds).

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: Allowing for the killing of old and sick specimens within the park area upon payment could become a source of funding for the territory. This happens already in the Slovenian side of Isonzo valley and in South Tyrol in Italy. Another activity to raise funds would be to allow for no-kill phishing (catch and release). The interviewee was not informed of any another funding source for the protection of biodiversity that might be used to give value to hunting as a sustainable management strategy for wildlife.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee mentioned projects such as SPARE (Strategic Alpine Resource) and others funded through EU mechanisms like cohesion funds. However, it was indicated that these projects were limited in scale and scope, with local communities sometimes receiving modest funding. Most funding opportunities are tied to specific projects, making it difficult to address ongoing or emerging needs outside of project timelines and constraints. Funding was reported as insufficient. This has led in the past to their absence from decision-making bodies like the TNP Council during certain periods due to a lack of resources.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: Funding for farmers within TNP came from both governmental sources and specific projects. For instance, the TNP provided grants to support innovative farming practices, such as purchasing equipment for dairy, cheese and ice cream production. The interviewee found this support beneficial but noted the overall insufficiency of resources for addressing challenges like wolf population management. Broader, systemic funding for cross-border cooperation was not discussed.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: Funding for biodiversity conservation and tourism collaboration primarily comes from European programs such as Alpine Space. National funding is minimal and directed toward parks and conservation authorities rather than tourism entities. The interviewee expressed the need for greater integration of tourism into biodiversity-related funding initiatives, not solely for financial support but to ensure that the tourism sector is included in decision-making and project design.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: Funding for transboundary conservation comes primarily from project-based sources, as national funding for this purpose is minimal. Flexibility is limited, and reliance on external funds creates inconsistencies. The interviewee deemed current funding insufficient, with governmental support cited as the key gap. The focus on specific species and European priority areas under Natura 2000 has sidelined other important conservation needs.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: The interviewee mentioned the presence of national funds [linked to MAB reserves, ed.], and that the PNPG and the TNP use EU funds through specific projects. The management

²³ <https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/alpslife/>.

of funds and human resources is complex for small municipalities. At national level, in the context of a call on climate change (*bando clima*) the Ministry of Environment (MASE) provides funds to municipalities located within the MAB Reserve. However, the interviewee underlined the difficulties to manage directly financial resources connected to the MAB Reserve with the limited human resources of the municipalities. The management of these resources, as well as the context and mechanisms to access them are complex, as municipalities are overwhelmed with other tasks and have to prioritize the provision of fundamental services. In this context, the municipalities are not able to plan and foresee how to use these resources yet. Plus, the municipalities are not able to fully access these mechanisms since they do not know how they work.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: On funding the interviewee said that they were not aware of specific funds linked in some way to the PNPG and made available to environmental associations. The main source of funding of these associations is voluntary work. Plus, they said that their association was not involved so far in any of the EU-funded projects managed by the parks on of which the parks are part.

2.4 Information on best practices and challenges of and for cross-border biodiversity conservation

What types of socio-economic activities which are influencing transboundary biodiversity conservation positively or negatively were listed by the interviewees?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: Tourism was indicated as an activity influencing both nature conservation and the well-being of local people with its economic effects. The situation with tourism is very different on the two sides of the border: much more developed on the Slovenian side, under development on the Italian side. In this sense, their idea is to make tourists aware that the Italian park is also part of the Julian Alps.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: Tourism is a socio-economic activity that influences the transboundary character of the cooperation between the PNPG and the TNP. The main seat of PNPG is located in Resia, which is at the border with Slovenia. Excursions have always been organized by both parks on the other side of the border. Furthermore, both parks are interested in monitoring the touristic fluxes, because PNPG aims to identify the most attractive sites, while the TNP has to limit its own visitors that are too many. That's why the idea is to reinforce the connection between the two parks, with connected bike lanes, common trekking paths, etc. Hunting is another activity that has been influencing the cooperation since the beginning. The existence of differences in the legislation on hunting between Italy and Slovenia (hunting permitted in Slovenia and prohibited in Italy) has prompted cooperation. Cooperation mainly occurs in the field of monitoring of and common research activities on species such as ibex, chamois, and bears. According to this interviewee, cooperation in this field happens not only at the park level, but also between Italian and Slovenian universities (University of Udine and the Slovenian Research Institute on Wildlife²⁴) as well as between Italian hunting reserves and Slovenian hunting families. Common projects are also implemented in this field, such as AlpBionet,²⁵ Dinalpconnect,²⁶ Nat2Care.²⁷ Cooperation in this field has not led to harmonization of legislation but to an increased awareness of the differences and an increased willingness to work together in this sector. According to this interviewee, the UNESCO MAB

²⁴ What the interviewee meant is probably the Slovenian Forest Institute.

²⁵ <https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/alpbionet2030/>.

²⁶ <https://dinalpconnect.adrioninterreg.eu/>.

²⁷ <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/nat2care>.

Transboundary Biosphere Reserve will favor cooperation in the hunting sector, because it could be used as leverage to discuss those issues at the competent table to solve the legislative gap. Agriculture is another relevant activity because farmers on both sides of the border face the same realities: small businesses in remote areas with the same kind of agricultural activities in place with a good potential when it comes to the authenticity of food products. The problems are also similar and are linked to the presence of large carnivores in the Julian Alps, such as the bear and the wolf. These issues are usually raised during the Annual Forum and the parks try to address them with common initiatives, such as the promotion of transboundary products or the presentation of products in events on the other side of the border. According to this interviewee, farmers are well aware of the importance of the transboundary dimension in this area.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: According to the interviewee, pasture can positively influence biodiversity conservation since it hinders reforestation and enables the maintenance of habitats that would otherwise be difficult to maintain. Similarly, the maintenance of trails is helpful since it facilitates accessing habitats and carrying out conservative/maintenance activities. Agriculture, in terms of cultural heritage and plant biodiversity, has a positive impact since it has a marginal character. Outdoor activities might have a negative impact if they increase in the future, like the use of e-bikes that could disrupt some habitats. A potential risk is also the development of ski facilities.

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: The interviewee underlined that hunting is a crucial issue in transboundary cooperation since the EU Birds and Habitats Directives give indications, but there is room for maneuver at national level and hunting legislations are national. The main issues are two: first, it is possible to hunt or not a certain species, and second, where it is possible to hunt: in some countries hunting is forbidden in all parks, in other countries hunting is permitted in regional parks. Transboundary cooperation often happens between parks of different categories and there may be the case that hunting is permitted on one side of the border but forbidden on the other. This issue cannot be tackled with an agreement between the parks, since this is decided by law. The parks can agree on issues that have an indirect impact (awareness raising campaigns, hunting calendars, etc.) but cannot change the law.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: Tourism was identified as having both a positive and negative influence. While it provides economic benefits and promotes conservation awareness, over-tourism strains ecosystems and increases human pressure on sensitive areas. Other activities, such as agricultural intensification in lowlands, abandonment of mountain pastures, and forestry practices using heavy machinery, were also noted as challenges. Historical practices, like the introduction of non-native fish species, have left long-term impacts on freshwater ecosystems.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: According to the interviewee many activities in the PNPG are positively influencing biodiversity conservation: farmers that pay attention to biodiversity conservation and work in synergy with the PNPG; researchers that are active within the PNPG. It is important to work together rather than randomly and without respecting biodiversity conservation. There are many good examples in the agricultural sector, like pasture management, mowing at the appropriate time, etc. On the one hand, there is an increasing awareness on biodiversity issues and a blooming of small economic activities respectful of biodiversity and willing to collaborate with the protected area that are beneficial for these territories; on the other hand, there are challenges for these activities as well, for instance, farmers face difficulties in accessing the compensation system for damages by large carnivores.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: Regarding the PNPG there are no big issues since there is only a small ski property, which is in the Julian Alps MAB Reserve but is marginal to the PNPG, and it is located in the transitional zone. However, the interviewee restated the importance of having activities in the MAB

Reserve to ensure a relationship between man and nature, otherwise the purpose of the MAB itself would be defeated.

Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI: The interviewee mentioned sustainable tourism and organic agriculture as potentially positive factors. For tourism to be sustainable visitors must be trained and media should contribute positively. The interviewee also highlighted that the tourism may be critical also in negative terms. Another negative factor is the excessive construction of infrastructures or the lack of a proper planning, which influences the connectivity of nature. In contrast, hunting was presented as an activity that does not have negative impacts on nature protection but that rather allows for an “active protection” of biodiversity. In this sense, hunting should not be judged under a sentimental lens that condemns the killing of animals as such.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: Tourism was identified as both an opportunity and a challenge. The interviewee praised the growth of ecotourism and the preservation of traditional knowledge and products in the region. However, they also expressed concern about the pressure from increased tourist numbers, which can overwhelm sensitive ecosystems if not managed properly. Additionally, challenges like illegal activities related to transportation, noise, and unregulated sports in natural areas were mentioned as threats to biodiversity.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: Tourism was identified as a significant pressure, particularly within the UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. Increased visitor numbers pose challenges to both biodiversity and the sustainability of local municipalities. However, the interviewee also emphasized the potential of ecological agriculture and nature conservation as avenues for regional development, particularly in border areas.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: This interviewee emphasized the positive role played by hunters, both in the creation of the park and in the reintroduction of ibex and marmot in the Prealpi Giulie. The first specimens were brought in the area by hunters from the Gran Paradiso Park. Then the park followed suit. Another good practice is the annual census of wildlife that hunting reserves do to identify the number and types of animals that can be killed. They have been collecting data for the past 20 years.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee mentioned tourism, particularly in the Julian Alps, as the main socioeconomic activity influencing transboundary biodiversity conservation.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: Tourism was highlighted as a significant factor, with over-tourism causing water pollution in peak seasons. Agriculture, while largely sustainable, faced pressures from wildlife (e.g., wolves attacking livestock) and environmental challenges like drought. The lack of effective management for these issues was seen as a barrier to sustainable conservation.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: Tourism was identified as both a challenge and an opportunity. The growth of summer tourism has led to increased visitor pressure on sensitive ecosystems, especially in core areas of the TNP. Issues such as inadequate sewage systems and the overuse of alpine huts have exacerbated environmental impacts. On the other hand, tourism supports local livelihoods and can be a tool for promoting conservation awareness, as demonstrated by initiatives like the Wildflower Festival.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The interviewee identified tourism and agriculture as key sectors affecting biodiversity. Tourism, particularly its rapid expansion in the Julian Alps, was described as the main challenge. Agricultural activities and land-use practices also play a role, requiring careful management to align with conservation goals.

What were identified as the main challenges the interviewees are facing in their daily work/life? What were identified as key mechanisms to deal with the challenges and emerging threats that impact biodiversity, if any?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: Balancing development needs that are met by tourism and conservation is one of the main challenges. One strategy is to advertise the Julian Alps as one area in order to move tourists from the Slovenian to the Italian side. To counter overtourism, they are trying to develop regulations, in collaboration with the competent ministries and in consultation with locals, to limit traffic in the mountains. There are resistances about them because of established customs (to visit the mountains) and because of economic interests. Other measures are to create quiet zones in the TNP that people are prohibited to enter and to connect the TNP and the PNPG with both walking and cycling trails. This is a plan within the Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. Another challenge is linked to the differences of the Italian and Slovenian legal systems, including differences in the form of the State and the competent institutions. When asked explicitly about the role of agriculture, the interviewee said that the presence of the wolf poses problems to farmers. At the same time farmers are present to a very limited extent in the territory of the park, but they are present in the MAB Biosphere Reserve.²⁸ They have a development department and dedicated funds within the TNP to deal with farmers' requests. Hybridization of the wolf with the dog is another challenge.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: One of the main challenges is to involve people, but in the interviewee's view this difficulty can be circumvented when talking about concrete problems. For instance, legislative differences do not allow farmers to sell their products on the other side of the border. Legislative differences are a challenge per se and are related to the differences in governance, and in particular to the fact that different levels of government are competent to regulate the parks' activities, the regional level in the case of PNPG and the national level for the TNP.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: According to the interviewee, a great challenge is overcoming localism and particularism, creating network and flows of data and information that are continuous and accessible to those managing biodiversity. What is needed is a change in the mindset and accepting sharing technical data, like those on large carnivores since they are the most problematic element for the creation of coexistence mechanisms. It would be important to capitalize on projects realized in the past and guarantee continuity to the results achieved.

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: Among the challenges of transboundary biodiversity conservation, in general terms, the interviewee highlighted the difficulties of working on Natura 2000 transboundary sites due to the different management/administrative systems involved across the border. The interview underlined that the EU Commission is also focusing on this aspect and cited the examples of managing the Wadden Sea and the whale sanctuary. In the latter case, cooperation is even more difficult since borders are invisible but, from an administrative point of view, sea zones are very complex and the national level is always present; hence, Ministries have to be involved.

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: One challenge is that social development in mountain areas is a very burdensome topic that does not pay well in terms of political consensus: Politicians tend not to deal with this issue because it does not change electoral equilibria. Mountain communities tend to remain isolated. From an ecological perspective, the main challenge is to ensure the existence of good quality ecological corridors, because only guaranteeing a good level of in-situ protection is not sufficient. Habitat fragmentation is therefore a big problem. In order to realize these green corridors, one should act on the

²⁸ Since the TNP is also the managing authority of the national MAB Biosphere Reserve, that is why the TNP is dealing with farmers' requests.

legislations that are usually different and touch upon different sectors, including transport, spatial planning, and biodiversity protection. Therefore, different actors need to be involved in the discussion. Plus, this topic needs necessarily to be tackled at supranational level, for instance within the ABB of the Alpine Convention, to overcome differences in national legislation. EGTCs are also good schemes in this sense, and the interviewee refers to a useful publication on this topic: Alessandro Fodella, Giuseppe Avolio, and Marco Pertile (2005) *Studio: Creazione di nuove forme di cooperazione transfrontaliera a livello sub-statale per lo sviluppo sostenibile del territorio*. Eurac research.²⁹ Another challenge is how to balance human presence and at the same time ensure the protection of nature, so the dual concept of biodiversity intended as nature and landscape (human presence). Monitoring biodiversity in mountainous areas is also complex, since there are no specific benchmarks and methodologies, although ISPRA (*Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale* – Institute for Environmental Protection and Research)³⁰ and the Alpine Space AlpsLife project are working on that. Creating red lists within the framework of IUCN would also be desirable. The problem with data elaborated by ISPRA is that these are not systematically shared, for instance, with Slovenia, sometimes because methodologies to collect data are different and therefore they are difficult to compare. Sometimes data are not shared for economic or political reasons. Monitoring can become more effective also thanks to those associations that voluntarily collect data (ex. birds associations). Another challenge the interviewee identifies is the problematic cooperation between the Alpine Convention and the macroregional EU strategy for the Alpine region EUSALP. The Italian Presidency of the Alpine Convention intends to work on that to make sure that EUSALP becomes the implementing arm of the Alpine Convention, as aimed for when the strategy was first conceived in 2011. The coordination table within the Italian Presidency of the Alpine Convention aims to involve different kind of actors, such as regional authorities and research centers, in the governance of the Alpine Convention. Alpine Convention experts currently sit also at the decision-making tables of EUSALP. The opposite is not always true, and this should be remedied.

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: In terms of challenges for transboundary biodiversity protection, the interviewee mentioned the four topics requiring cooperation in the framework of the Alpine Convention: conservation, connectivity, restoration, and monitoring. In terms of conservation, the challenge is agreeing on a list of species and habitats that should be prioritized to improve their conservation status. The challenge linked to connectivity is rearranging the distribution of some species and tackling fragmentation to enhance ecological functionality. On restoration the challenge is again connected to prioritizing some areas and issues, like pollinators and peatlands, which are very specific habitats and key for the Alps, and river connectivity.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: The interviewee raised attention on the continuous loss of biodiversity, especially outside protected areas. One of the main focuses of work is thus connected to increasing ecological connectivity among protected areas and reducing negative effects of biodiversity loss across the regional territory as a whole. A critical issue is the difference among legal systems, the presence of different organizations, different administrations, and different States: all these elements make working on ecological connectivity outside protected areas even more difficult. Being within the EU is helpful since States refer to the same Directives and play on a common field, which facilitates working on this kind of topics [ecological connectivity and biodiversity, ed.]. The interviewee reflected also on the different approach adopted between EU environmental obligations and funds. On the one hand, the Habitat and Birds Directives do not foresee transboundary actions but adopt a national/regional approach rather than a transboundary one. On the other hand, EU funds (Interreg and other environmental programs) have a cooperative approach. Cooperation applies to single projects, which do not lead to a process of legal alignment, and once the projects are concluded the partners keep working within their respective and

²⁹ Please note that Federica Cittadino has a paper copy of this study (Italian only), if anybody is interested.

³⁰ Public body under the supervision of the MASE.

different national legal frameworks. A challenge for mountain territories is the proliferation of hydroelectric power units and the consequent water scarcity in watercourses. This problem should be managed since, on the one hand, there is the request for renewable energy, but in some cases their effectiveness is low and fictitious in terms of energy efficiency while their impact they might have in conservation terms is high. According to the interviewee, fragmentation is also due to the accumulation of new structures and infrastructures – which might be needed and useful – without getting rid of old and useless ones. All of them impact conservation. Biodiversity management through human presence is a challenge since depopulation and the abandonment of mountain areas is leading to reforestation (low quality wood) that reduces biodiversity and has a drastic impact on species like amphibians, reptiles, and insects. On the other hand, the macro fauna (ungulates, large carnivores) is increasing in an unexpected way. In terms of cooperation, one of the issues is that the Italian national level is not aware of the deep level of cooperation in the Julian Alps. In responding to the question on how to evaluate effectiveness, the interviewee said that monitoring is key in contrasting all challenges related to biodiversity protection: In particular, one should monitor that measures to counter threats to biodiversity are implemented.,

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI: Borders still constitute an important cultural barrier. UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserves help to overcome this type of barriers, also between Italian regions when applicable. This recognition, moreover, gives a lot of maneuvering space: objectives are recognized internationally but then stakeholders are free to decide how to reach them. Therefore, a clear advantage of this way of cooperating is flexibility. The way in which the global objectives of the UNESCO MAB program are to be reached is left to the local communities' decision. The main challenges in the development of the candidature were the involvement of the national MAB committees that were officially responsible for presenting the candidature. The relationship with the national governments of both countries was so problematic that until the very last minute they feared they would not make it in time to present the candidature. What was lacking was a joint statement signed by both governments, which eventually was signed. One of the main weaknesses of the cooperation in the Julian Alps coincides with its major strength, that is the well-developed cooperation among the parks. Parks are so active and capable that the risk is that the other stakeholders delegate every activity to them. In the framework of the UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserve is, therefore, important that the parks take a step back and stimulate other actors to build ownership. The limit of having only the parks active in this sense is of course that they lack the necessary (staff) resources to carry all the work on their own. A weakness of the Italian side of the cooperation is the fact that they are perceived and treated as marginal, and therefore they are isolated even within their region.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: The main challenges include legislative discrepancies between countries, managing over-tourism, and addressing species-specific issues like ibex and chamois management. Efforts to harmonize species management practices, particularly for large carnivores and alpine fauna, have faced encounter barriers as legislation diverges between countries. The interviewees stressed the importance of long-term planning and systemic collaboration to address challenges effectively. They highlighted the value of leveraging EU regulations and UNESCO recognition to promote conservation and raise public awareness. Despite these efforts, the absence of harmonized legislation and a lack of systemic national support hinder the implementation of broader strategies. While the parks have developed informal mechanisms to address urgent issues, long-term solutions require greater national and regional support. They also emphasized challenges such as the shift from a holistic to a segregational approach in nature conservation, given their role as a natural park (that mandates to conserve nature as an entity) while also being the responsible institution for Natura 2000 management, which is a typical segregational process. Limited resources and the need to rely on personal networks was also mentioned as a challenge. Funding for transboundary conservation relies heavily on EU projects, as national legislation prevents public funds from being used for international cooperation. This dependence creates challenges in sustaining long-term initiatives, as activities often cease when project funding ends. Other activities, such as agricultural

intensification in lowlands, abandonment of mountain pastures, and forestry practices using heavy machinery, were also noted as challenges. For instance, historical practices, like the introduction of non-native fish species, have left long-term impacts on freshwater ecosystems.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: An issue that emerged in the PNPG was depopulation and the difficulty to involve/attract the attention of youth between 18 and 30 years old. In the TNP the involvement of youth has been disregarded in the last decade, and thus there is no involvement of young adults as it is in the Italian side. In addition, the interviewee mentioned the challenges that farmers face in accessing the compensation system for damages by large carnivores. The issue of large carnivores emerged as problematic, especially for hunters and breeders, and the different legal frameworks between IT and SI have an impact as well within the communities. The problem is recreating a socio-cultural context in which large carnivores are foreseen, but this is a long process – not impossible though – and parks are supporting it. According to the interviewee another challenge is restoring grassland areas. There are good practices, like those of the Stregna Municipality Land Association, but the results are still limited despite the conspicuous financial resources available to this purpose. These poor results are due to excessive land fragmentation and the difficulties in tackling this latter issue both by local administration and land associations. A transboundary challenge is the management of Alpine ungulates especially in connection to the mange disease (*rogna*) in the last decade. Management practices evolved since the '90s, animals are not moved easily from one area to another, and new strategies are being sought to create a resistant population of ibex and chamois in the Julian Alps. Another challenge is connected to griffon nesting areas and there are many more.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: According to the interviewee, the main challenge is making the local administrations within the MAB (both in IT and SI) aware of the importance of being a UNESCO area, since this has not been perceived yet. There is the need to understand the implications of being both a national and transboundary UNESCO MAB Reserve since this is an important leverage for local development. The interviewee noticed a wider participation of Slovenian stakeholders in support of the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, while it was underlined – based on private discussions the interviewee had – that the national Slovenian MAB Reserve was a top-down process promoted under the ex-Yugoslavia and not a participatory one. A challenge is the low population in the area, and the efforts to motivate young people to stay are meant to ensure that people live, maintain, and protect these areas and the nature therein. Otherwise, there is excessive reforestation over grassland, and animals that move to other areas. Human presence cannot be limited to tourists, but there is the need of residents, tutors, custodians to maintain these areas. The interviewee also mentioned several times the marginalization of the area and depopulation.

Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI: As a consequence of excessive construction (for instance for the realization of skiing facilities) or defective planning, the fragmentation of the environment and habitats and the lack of connectivity are the main challenges for the area. The body to which the interviewee belongs may contribute to face this challenge through its service for the protection of forests, where police meets regularly (several times a year) with rangers and other officers to monitor these developments on the field, and then communicate the results of this monitoring to the competent authorities. According to this interviewee, hunting is not a threat, because hunters have well developed ethical principles, and in case any wrongdoing were committed, this would immediately be reported or become known. In general terms, punishments and sanctions as a way to contrast challenges are not effective mechanisms to counter threats. On the contrary, compromises have to be struck. Another negative phenomenon is that of weeds, especially when it comes to forests that have tremendously enlarged their coverage (36% in 1860, almost 60-80% today). This is due to pasture retreat and forest cover increase, phenomena started in the 1960s: the abandonment of agricultural land that, when unutilized, is quickly covered by forests.

This phenomenon is linked to the fact that some species are disappearing, such as the hare (*lepre*) and the *francolino di monte*, while some others are increasingly widespread, such as the boar and the deer, whose presence is excessive nowadays. In the view of the interviewee, this contributes to landscape change. To contrast this phenomenon, the interviewee's body is increasing the number of legal cullings of these animals, although they encounter the resistance of hunters because it requires the killing of fertile females. Monitoring these species is also a strategy they implement to decide how many cullings are allowed per year. This decision is based on various data collected by hunter families, such as the body mass of male deer, the status of young vegetation, damages caused by wildlife, etc. The collection of these data is mandatory for hunter families by law. The interviewee did not know whether these monitoring data are shared with the Italian counterpart.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: Key challenges include legislative differences between countries, increased human activity in natural areas, and balancing tourism with conservation. The interviewee emphasized the need for stronger regulation and management to address issues such as illegal driving in nature and the ecological impact of tourism. They advocated for shared strategies and tools to mitigate these challenges while promoting sustainable development. The interviewee highlighted the value of initiatives like the UNESCO MAB Reserves and European conservation projects in promoting collaboration and fostering innovative approaches to shared challenges. Additionally, challenges like illegal activities related to transportation, noise, and unregulated sports in natural areas were mentioned as threats to biodiversity.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: Challenges include inconsistencies in protection regimes across borders, limited funding, and managing competing land-use interests, such as tourism. For example, the differing designations of protected areas between Slovenia and neighboring countries complicate coordinated management. The interviewee highlighted the role of transboundary cooperation in creating opportunities for remote regions, particularly along Slovenia's southern border with Croatia. Mechanisms to address these challenges include harmonizing legislative approaches, enhancing collaboration through bilateral commissions, and leveraging networks like Alparc for knowledge sharing.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: One of the main challenges is depopulation. Another challenge is the negative perceptions that farmers have of the parks, because both of the contrasting interests between agriculture and biodiversity conservation and the perceived administrative burdens and limitations. The support of farmers and also local administration to the MAB and the cooperation also depend on politics, the change in elected decision-makers. There is also a lack of awareness on the part of farmers that preserving biodiversity is important for agriculture and that being part of a natural park and a biosphere reserve might be an opportunity also for their business. This challenge is linked to the fact that, according to this interviewee, farmers have been not involved in decision-making processes. Farmers have been affected only by top-down decisions. The role of agriculture in preserving pastures and grasslands is recognized in words, but it does not receive the necessary funding. This produces the advancement of woodland and consequent loss of biodiversity. Another challenge in this sense is the small sizes of agricultural enterprises (land fragmentation) – the average size of property is 200 m², which makes the economic and administrative burden on these activities excessive. These farms are not economically sustainable because their productivity is very low. Land and property fragmentation makes it extremely difficult for farmers to access available funds, such as the Rural Development Programs (RDPs – *Programmi di Sviluppo Rurale* in Italian). Another challenge mentioned by this interviewee is that Region FVG is not active in the existing transboundary institutional tables on agriculture, which involve Serbia, Croatia, Austria, Italy, and Hungary. So, there is no institutional backing of transboundary cooperation in the field and dialogue and information exchange is insufficient. The decision-making path in Italy is perceived as an obstacle. On this last point, the interviewee said: “the first obstacle is I propose something, I highlight problems, but I become afraid, and I stop. It is difficult to find a solution, the path to find a common solution, mountain

community, region and ministry, if it is necessary...it seems to us that laws and regulations are like stones, like the gravity force, a state of things, dogma that we cannot modify". The role of public powers should be to sustain private firms to adopt more sustainable agricultural practice; instead, the risk of these innovations is left entirely upon private firms. The paths to get the funds available at the regional level for instance to encourage the maintenance of pastures are too complex and burdensome (also the requirements for a mowing to be considered as such), and parks cannot invest specific money on that because they have limited agricultural firms within the territory of the park. The fact also that some properties are managed by tenants makes these incentives not very attractive because tenants who receive money for mowing (*sfalcio*) are required to do that even when their rental contract expires, otherwise they get fined. The excessive presence of administrative burdens is also a cause for depopulation. A way to counter the challenges of the agricultural sector is to create added-value in the production and to promote the development of supply chains (*filiere*), for instance if a farmer produces hay, then they have to use it to breed animals to then produce meat or milk. Some of these traditional supply chains, for instance the *latterie turnarie* (milk producers conferring their milk to a cooperative and cooperation in turn to produce cheese and milk products), were abandoned. The lack of awareness of the opportunities offered by the existence of the parks and the Biosphere Reserve is partially mitigated by the presence of young farmers. The loss of biodiversity, monocultures, and intensive farming are considered a problem for agriculture by the interviewee. However, they recognize that this loss of biodiversity is not perceived as a problem by farmers.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: According to this interviewee, one of the challenges is that hunters are slowly disappearing because youth is less and less interested in this practice. This has a negative effect on the possibility that hunters effectively carry out the legal slaughter of animals/culling (*abbattimento*), which has negative effects both on sick or hurt animals and on biodiversity. The way in which the park is regulated represents also a challenge in view of the interviewee, because the structure of the park is modeled too much in line with the national law on protected areas. This means that many activities are not allowed in the park and that the park is seen only as a bureaucratic machine by local people. Linked to that is the presence of large mammals, like wild boars and deer, whose excessive presence produces damages to forest habitats. Given the policies against hunting and the decreasing number of hunters, the interviewee foretells that in some years it will be necessary to pay people to kill animals to control the expansion of certain species. In anthropized areas, like that of the Julian Alps, the responsible management of fauna/wildlife is necessary. This implies that if animals are to be killed, they should die immediately without suffering. The killing should therefore be done professionally and not by local inhabitants that want to defend themselves from an intruding and dangerous wolf or bear. The interview emphasizes that there are hunters with a professionalism and a serious ethics, and these need to be involved in the management of species. The creation of buffer zones (*aree contigue*) where hunting activities are allowed only for residents could be a solution, but hunters do not trust decision-makers on that anymore because of changes in the conception of the park (see 2.8 below) and because the past director of the PNPG had interrupted the relationship with hunters. The new director is trying to recreate a climate of trust. In this sense, hunting would allow for the coexistence of wildlife with men in anthropized areas. Allowing for the killing of old and sick specimens within the park area upon payment could become furthermore a source of funding for the territory. This activity should be guided by local hunters that know well the territory and the development phase/health conditions of the single specimens. Hunting is meaningful as a management strategy only if there is a link between the hunters and their territory: usually serious hunters have a profound knowledge of the local specimens. And they could feed the park managers with this knowledge, for instance by indicating which specimens are to be killed.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee mentioned the political nature of leadership positions in entities like the TNP, including the directorship. This was criticized as a barrier to

effective governance, suggesting that politically motivated appointments undermined expertise and long-term planning. The interviewee also reflected on the need to change the capitalist paradigm toward growth as it leads to consumption of natural resources. The need to think about reducing growth to protect biodiversity was mentioned. The interviewee highlighted the impact of tourism's strain on local infrastructure, such as wastewater systems, transport networks, and housing availability. This socio-economic pressure exacerbates challenges for both biodiversity and local communities. The tourist infrastructure in places like the TNP is under pressure, leading to issues like transport bottlenecks and inadequate wastewater management systems. For instance, rivers being contaminated by untreated wastewater due to the inability of infrastructure to handle the influx of visitors during peak seasons. Tourism-related activities, such as mass events (e.g., concerts in fragile ecosystems like Lago di Fusine), were criticized for causing ecological harm, including habitat destruction and pollution. Secondly, pollution from agriculture and mountain huts was also mentioned. In particular because of lack of proper wastewater management. The interviewee mentioned divergent legislative frameworks, particularly in spatial planning, as a major barrier to seamless cooperation. Slovenia lacks regional administrative levels, unlike Italy, and this difference creates challenges in harmonizing strategies. Additionally, the interviewee also highlighted that most funding opportunities are tied to specific projects, making it difficult to address ongoing or emerging needs outside of project timelines and constraints.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: The key challenges identified were the following: firstly, wildlife management due to the high wolf populations threatening livestock, requiring EU law changes and active management by the park. Secondly, environmental changes such as droughts and shallow soils pose long-term threats. Thirdly, overtourism constitutes a challenge. Finally, the encroachment of forests into agricultural land was seen as detrimental to both biodiversity and farming. Mechanisms to address these challenges included better management practices, strategic use of agricultural land as buffer zones, and more robust representation of farmers in decision-making. The interviewee was critical of the lack of studies examining the socio-economic impacts of biodiversity conservation measures, which hindered informed decision-making. However, they stressed that transboundary conservation efforts need synchronization across countries to be impactful. Overall, there was a sense that the cooperation mechanism relied on operational, not strategic alignment, focusing on immediate ecological issues rather than systemic collaboration.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee identified seasonality and the pressure of mass (mostly summer) tourism as significant challenges. They emphasized the need for effective visitor management systems, such as shuttle services to reduce car use and the development of alternative tourism products like the Julian Alps Trail to disperse visitor flows. Another challenge is the impact of climate change, which influences tourism demand and poses risks to local ecosystems. The interviewee stressed the importance of collaboration with conservation authorities and innovative solutions to mitigate these impacts. They stressed the need for collaborative approaches involving diverse stakeholders to address complex challenges and ensure the long-term health of both biodiversity and local communities. At the same time, the interviewee noted gaps in institutional coordination between sectors, particularly at the national level. They expressed frustration at the lack of integration between ministries responsible for tourism, agriculture, and nature conservation, which hinders effective cross-border collaboration.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The main challenges include overtourism, fueled by the rapid growth in tourism infrastructure that strains natural resources and habitats; legislative disparities as differences in national regulations hinder seamless cooperation; and wildlife crime because phenomena such as illegal hunting (e.g., bears and capercaillie) highlight cross-border enforcement challenges. Mechanisms to address these challenges include initiating new projects, focusing on sustainable tourism, and improving state-level cooperation. The interviewee expressed optimism about an upcoming cohesion-funded project that aims to address overtourism in cooperation with the TNP. Additionally, the interview also

reckoned that the focus on specific species and European priority areas under Natura 2000 has sidelined other important conservation needs.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: In the PNPG, a key challenge is conceiving biodiversity protection as a comprehensive concept that combines natural protection with preserving opportunities for inhabitants in mountain areas. The aim is to counteract depopulation trends and offer them a new perspective linked to the Transboundary MAB Reserve and opportunities in this context. The challenge now is identifying the contents linked to the transboundary UNESCO MAB recognition and ensuring the presence of people that know the value of this area and transfer it to others. Local administrators need to work for local communities living within the area of the PNPG and MAB Reserve to ensure that they remain active and productive communities: People stay as families, since they can work and live in these areas, and new families come thanks to possibilities that are also connected to the park and the MAB Reserve. The interviewee mentioned a repopulation project that is taking place in their areas: “Come to live and work in mountain areas” (*Vieni a vivere e lavorare in montagna*) with the cooperative Cramars from Tolmezzo and Fondazione Friuli. More than 400 families applied to move to the area of Resia and its surroundings, since they find themselves in line with values, lifestyle, and good practices applied in these mountain areas. There is an exchange with these families: They learn about the area and exchange with the local community to get to know each other and understand if they want to move and contribute to the community. Even if local actors know about the Julian Alps Reserve, they do not know the real implications and fully perceive the potential benefits. Therefore, it is important to develop concrete actions and projects connected to the Biosphere Reserve and transform it into an opportunity for all. Another challenge is ensuring the survival of biodiversity by being present (*presidiare*) in the area, facing emerging challenges, including climate change, and thus being able to operate preventively as well as managing emergencies. Maintaining biodiversity entails finding a balance between nature and people. This is true for socio-economic activities like tourism: One should take advantage of transboundary trends by supporting the Slovenian side of the MAB Reserve to better manage overtourism. Cooperating in this sector means increasing the presence of hotel, restaurants, shops of local handicrafts and offering mountain guides on the Italian side. Tourist facilities on the IT side were strongly impacted by the 1976 earthquake and not reconstructed. The difficulties linked to the limited human resources available in small municipalities emerged again when speaking about relations, collaborations, and initiatives with SI border municipalities or other operating the wider networks. The PNPG offers its support (for instance to understand how to access funds and use them) and facilitates the involvement of local actors whenever possible (in initiatives, projects etc.). For the interviewee, gaining the UNESCO Transboundary Biosphere Reserve is a result that should not be taken for granted since being a border area implies being a land to be conquered, with a difficult history and resistance to some projects. Moreover, there are only 25 transboundary MAB Reserves in the world, which means that it is difficult to achieve this objective, and that there is a group of people working for that and committed to such a project. However, the transboundary MAB recognition is just a starting point, because it entails creating opportunities for this area that become opportunities for all.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: Concerning challenges, the interviewee said that the area is anthropized in a very limited way, so the human presence per se does not produce challenges for biodiversity. Quite on the contrary, depopulation can be identified as a challenge. One of the projects to contrast depopulation is “*Vieni a vivere in montagna*”³¹ (Come and live in the mountains), promoted in the context of 7 remote villages, including the municipality of Resia that is within the territory of the PNPG. Depopulation also has an impact on the quality of public services and the possibility of local authorities to provide them. Climate change was mentioned as a challenge. And tourism was considered a challenge, especially when it comes to rebalancing the touristic flows that are too abundant in Slovenia and too less developed in Italy. When

³¹ <https://www.vieniavivereinmontagna.it/>.

asked explicitly on large carnivores, the interviewee said that their presence is more limited than in Trentino [another Italian region, the Autonomous Province of Trento, where the problem of cohabitation is very acute, ed.]. Numbers are more limited and economic operators are compensated for the damages, although they lament a long wait to obtain money. In their view, to prevent this problem that is only embryonic, one should follow the good practices available at national level, including more advanced fences, as well as investments to develop the culture of cohabitation between humans and large carnivores that is possible. Digitalization, in order to map and jointly monitor where these carnivores are located and how they move, would be another powerful measure. According to the interviewee the fact that in Trentino this topic has led to polarization is a sign of bad governance. Improving participation and public involvement in transboundary cooperation has also been cited as something to be improved (see section 2.7 below).

Were there any relevant differences or commonalities identifiable between the interviewees in how they perceived the challenges and the ability to deal with them within the cooperative mechanism?

Some interviewees agreed on the fact that legislative and institutional differences are a challenge (8 out of 2022). Habitat fragmentation, reforestation of lowlands, and excessive tourism were also mentioned by several stakeholders as important challenges. Lack of awareness, for instance of the importance of the MAB designation or of the link between agriculture and conservation, has been mentioned as a challenge across countries. Lack of funding is also lamented by several stakeholders as an issue that hinders cooperation at different levels and, in different ways, for different sets of stakeholders. Low and deficient involvement of some categories in decision-making is also a shared challenge, especially perceived so by hunters, farmers, and environmental organizations. Depopulation is also clearly a perceived challenge among Italian interviewees. Specific sectoral challenges have been mentioned by farmers and hunters, especially among the Italian representatives.

Were the interviewees able to identify benefits which arise from transboundary cooperation?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: A major benefit is the sharing of information, for instance about species (monitoring where they are located, but also long-term plans for their protection). An important advantage of their cooperation is that, when they have a local problem, they can ask their transboundary or foreign partners, like the PNPG and others to share their solutions to particular problems. With the back-up of these experiences, the TNP can make its voice and position better heard vis-à-vis Slovenian decision-makers.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The interviewee responded more on the benefits they want to obtain from the transboundary cooperation, mentioning the centrality of tourism not only as an economic activity but also as a resource that allows to raise awareness on the importance of the Julian Alps area. Another important benefit that emerged during the conversation is the exchange of best practices, that also comes from the fact that the PNPG is within the European networks mentioned above, such as Alparc. According to the interviewee cooperation is a plus since it provides for a general added value, including for the possibility to access additional projects funds that give the opportunity to be creative and take risks, and thus plan in a creative way.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: For the interviewee benefits are linked to knowing and informing each other about realities that are homogeneous and connected. A second important benefit is learning from both

good practices and mistakes made by others: The exchange of information and opportunity to solve together challenges or receiving inputs on issues that others have already addressed are all crucial. The fact that this is automatic, relatively easy, and for free is very important for the interviewee. This exchange is easy and fast, almost automatic with the TNP, while with other realities it is possible thanks to the participation in Alparc and EUROPARC (which works better than Federparchi).

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: According to the interviewee, when dealing with nature and conservation, borders need to be overcome as a concept, since borders are human infrastructures. It is not possible to conceive the protection or management of a species without applying a transboundary approach. The real question is: why is there no cooperation? Because it is complex, requires time, there are linguistic barriers, there are problems of funds; but there are no doubts on the reasons for cooperating. When discussing the benefit of cooperation, the interviewee highlighted also the importance of being in a network like EUROPARC. The added value of being in the network is exchanging experiences with other protected areas and creating synergies with others. The support of other parks, as well as of organizations like EUROPARC, is especially important when a cooperation process is undergoing “down” periods, also in psychological terms, since the park officer is not alone with its counterpart, but is part of a strong network. Another added value of cooperation emerges when pollution or other problems arise, as cited in section 2.5 for the Scarpe-Escaut case. Another example mentioned by the interviewee was in the case of fires that happen on one side of the border but provoke disasters on the other side. It was recalled a case in 2022 between Germany and Czech Republic: Thanks to the cooperation process, the reaction was faster, and international support (national army) could be provided immediately.

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: The transboundary management of species should be aimed to ensure that individual specimens of a species may continue to spread their genetic material across borders and therefore beyond the borders created artificially by men. This is related to ecological connectivity that is very important in the context of the Alpine arc and of the Alpine Convention. The interviewee also added that transboundary cooperation on biodiversity protection is fundamental for ensuring the EU and international objectives of nature protection and restoration, as well as the development of communication channels between different actors at different levels, from local communities to national administrations. The interviewee also defined the MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve scheme as a “unique platform of cooperation and sharing of both knowledge and best practices”³².

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: What emerged in the interview was a more general remark on the importance of transboundary cooperation networks like Alparc, which is the network of protected areas in the Alps. Alparc enables the collection of data on the status of Alpine biodiversity and good practices of protected areas, facilitates exchanges among protected areas. This knowledge and work is essential to enable cooperation at political level as well. Cooperation gives the chance to learn from each other and be inspired by other countries examples and thus pursue more ambitious objectives.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: Since in FVG there are many cyrillic-balcanic species, it is necessary to take into consideration how these species are managed across the border, in Slovenia, Croatia, and other Balkan countries. To this purpose, informal meetings with the National Institute for Nature Conservation of Nova Gorica and contacts - outside/beyond funded projects - aimed to understand the management of specific species and habitats in Slovenia (e.g. Karstic arid meadows) in order to manage them in a coordinate way and be more effective. Moreover, operating within the EU framework facilitates the comparison with other experiences, for instance, Slovenia and Austria have different approaches to the identification of Natura 2000 sites. In Slovenia, the Natura 2000 system covers 36% of the national territory, while in

³² Own translation.

Austria covers the 15%. The latter has many Natura 2000 sites, but very small and the approach is strategically oriented to protect specific species and habitats in a very effective way, like in the case of the beaver which was a conservation target in the Danube. Then the species can spread beyond protected areas. A couple of beavers arrived in FVG from AT and also the latter, they arrived naturally and their spread is a consequence not only of the abandonment of Alpine territories, but also – as in the case of the otter – of the improved water quality in rivers. Therefore, the application of the Water Framework Directive brought indirectly good results for biodiversity conservation. Reintroduction projects are limited to plant species and not applied to animal.

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI: Biodiversity, ecosystems, and culture do not know borders. Transboundary cooperation in this field may help counter both the inefficiencies of segmented action and the over efficiency of non-coordinated policies (for instance the excessive presence of the bear in Trentino that does not migrate because this species is treated too differently in Austria, Switzerland, and even in South Tyrol). One of the major strengths of the Julian Alps is the well-developed cooperation among the PNPG and the TNP due to historical and cultural reasons. In the view of the interviewee, geographically the mountains shared by the parks are one and the same, although they have been separated for historical reasons. The communities on both sides of the borders are in similar conditions, know each other, and are not in conflict with one another. The quality of cooperation projects carried out in this area is also a strength. Cooperation in the Julian Alps is therefore a state of affairs (*stato di fatto*). Julian Alps may become a pilot region for other mountain areas in the Alps, because the Alps have plenty of examples of communities separated by borders but that share history and culture. So, in this sense, the Julian Alps might become trend-setters.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: The interviewees highlighted the benefits of knowledge exchange, joint planning, and coordinated action, particularly for species management and visitor regulation. These collaborations foster mutual learning and help align conservation efforts across borders, despite the challenges posed by differing national priorities and frameworks.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: The interviewee highlighted that the PNPG and the TNP are very different in terms of size and governance (the TNP is national, with a centralized management and funded in a different way). Despite that, a lot was achieved during the years in aligning wildlife and floristic census techniques to have comparable data that can be kept. The main objective of cooperation is preserving the unique value of the Julian Alps for their peculiarity in geologic, biological, morphologic, and climatic terms. Cooperation between the parks aims to create a framework that addresses both a general objective of biodiversity conservation and more specific objectives for the conservation of specific species or habitats. Being different is identified as a plus since in the two parks different issues happen, and the examples or solutions developed in one park can be useful for the other. For instance, the TNP worked for many years to promote tourism, but once tourists arrived, the park was not ready for them. Therefore, diversity can be both a challenge and a benefit, and there is the will of the parks to identify conservation objectives that are as homogenous as possible to ensure protection uniformly. According to the interviewee some projects, like those connected to the ECST (EUROPARC), created a good network of territorial socio-economic actors (farmers, restaurant and hotel owners, tourism operators). A consequence was the creation of a team spirit and collaborations. For young people involved in biodiversity conservation and cooperation, benefits are connected to the opportunities offered by the EUROPARC Federation that is focusing and investing on youth, for instance through the creation of a youth officer position fully dedicated to youth involvement. Further opportunities for youth emerge in the context of the UNESCO MAB network. In 2024, the interviewee participated in the EuroMAB conference, and there was a strong presence of young people coming from biosphere reserves from all over Europe and North America.

Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI: The interviewee explicitly said that nature does not know national boundaries and that is why it is important to cooperate in the field of wildlife management at the transboundary level, both to preserve habitats, life Alpine mountains, and species that live in these habitats, like bears, wolves, and lynxes. Transboundary cooperation may furthermore facilitate the representation and exchange of views, as well as mutual learning. This in turn allows for enhanced knowledge that may improve wildlife management. These contacts may in addition facilitate agreements, like the ban on ibex killing between Italian and Slovenian counterparts.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: The interviewee viewed transboundary cooperation as essential for addressing issues that transcend borders, such as climate change, water management, and biodiversity conservation. They stressed that effective cooperation can enhance the success of shared initiatives and create benefits for the entire region.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: The interviewee saw transboundary biodiversity cooperation as a means to foster sustainable regional development, improve ecological connectivity, and align local practices with global conservation goals. These efforts not only support biodiversity but also enhance the quality of life for local communities by promoting sustainable economic activities.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: The exchange of best practices and successful models might be a positive side of cooperation, but it is not ongoing because also Slovenian farmers are overburdened with prohibitions and administrative requirements, and mountain agriculture is under stress also due to climate change everywhere in mountainous areas, including Slovenia. Other benefits that the interviewee sees are the creation of cooperation projects, and the development of supply chains (*filiere*). Cooperating to influence the administrative side of cooperation (like in the case of TRANSNATURE) is perceived in positive terms. The creation of ecological corridors was cited also as a positive impact of cooperation.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee mentioned initiatives like the visitor management plans implemented by the TNP, efforts to promote heritage interpretation in the area connected to the Peace Park initiative [heritage interpretation refers to the way of communicating visitors information about the place they are visiting, in this case related to the notion of Peace Park,³³ ed.], and cross border cooperation to protect glaciers as examples of benefits from transboundary cooperation.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: The interviewee noted the theoretical benefits of synchronized wildlife management (e.g., regulating deer and wolf populations) but could not identify tangible outcomes from existing cooperation mechanisms. Benefits for agriculture were unclear due to limited interaction between Slovenian and Italian farmers.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee viewed transboundary cooperation as a valuable opportunity to address shared challenges, such as tourism pressure and biodiversity loss, through joint strategies. Initiatives under the Biosphere Reserve framework provide a platform for collaboration, with potential benefits including improved visitor management, cross-border tourism promotion, and shared learning experiences.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The interviewee highlighted benefits such combining efforts with other actors such as TNP to pursue common goals, fostering sustainable tourism, and unifying conservation efforts

³³ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Heritage_interpretation.

across borders to address ecological threats. These collaborations also offer opportunities for broader stakeholder engagement.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: According to the interviewee, being a municipality within the park is an opportunity that has to be guided: the international recognitions should be followed by concrete actions and a new way of conceiving the future of the municipality within the park. Biodiversity conservation is very important for the area, and this is demonstrated by the commitment to pursuing the cooperation project with Slovenia and the TNP: becoming first a Biosphere Reserve in 2019 and then a transboundary MAB Reserve. Another benefit of cooperation is the opportunity to exchange constantly with the TNP and local administrators on the SI side, and to learn about their initiatives. It was underlined the strong commitment of the PNPG and the TNP to the cooperation project, as well as of other local stakeholders that were involved in the transboundary MAB reserve candidature and supported it.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: The main benefits identified of transboundary cooperation were linked to the fact the nature does not know any borders. This was illustrated by the examples of transboundary projects described in section 2.1. Plus, the interviewee added, cooperation is very important to establish transboundary relations that are significant also beyond conservation objectives. These relations may promote initiatives in other (related) fields.

2.5 Information on wildlife crime and pollution

Were the interviewees aware of any activities that are contributing to the direct, quantitative loss of biodiversity or activities that involves the killing, destruction, or taking of specimens of protected wild fauna or flora with a cross-border impact? Which activities, if at all, were listed?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: Nothing huge is going on. As a consequence, there is no transboundary cooperation on that aspect.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The limited poaching activities present in the PNPG have very limited effects in terms of biodiversity loss. The interviewee mentioned also poaching activities affecting the wolf. Rangers and forest guards are anyway provided by the Region FVG, whereas the parks are only informed of these activities [the PNPG does not have a direct role when it comes to enforcement, ed.]. The way in which the parks cooperate in this sector is to inform each other about episodes of poaching that however are then dealt with nationally.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: Although there are episodes of poaching (which are not constant but have had a higher or lower intensity depending on the year), these are limited in numbers and on few species. Patrolling is strongly ensured, and perpetrators bear judicial consequences. In some cases, the park became a civil party in proceeding against poachers, despite the poor results. There is no transboundary impact, and no transboundary measure is foreseen. The interviewee knew about limited poaching episodes in the TNP as well. Nevertheless, it was highlighted that it could be important to explore this issue further to understand if actually there are a few cases or if there is a lack of knowledge of their impact since this issue is not addressed.

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: The interviewee does not have any knowledge of this kind of crime in the Julian Alps. A more general reflection was that in Europe crimes are addressed at the national level, and national judges are competent. However, the European Court of Human Rights may start dealing more and more

with environmental crimes since the right to a healthy environment is recognized as a human right, but this will have a political more than a judicial impact. Cooperation on preventing wildlife crime varies depending on the countries: if forest rangers belong to the parks, this can be a topic of cooperation. If, like in IT, forest rangers are as State corps, then it depends on the relation between the park director and the local commander (*comandante del posto*).

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: The main issue about assessing crimes is the existence of an adequate monitoring system, which is very difficult in mountain regions. Usually monitoring is species specific (wolves, bears, lynx, birds, etc.). ISPRA is very important in this sense. IUCN red lists are not developed for mountainous habitats. Therefore, this would be an important goal to achieve in the future. The project AlpsLife aims to advance on Alpine monitoring.

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: The interviewee does not have knowledge of such crimes in Alpine protected areas, not even on large carnivores. Within the Alpine Convention the discussion relates to the possibility of hunting those species or not. On crimes, the interviewee cited the Bern Convention as the international term of reference.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: The interviews said that infractions were marginal, and they are not relevant.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: No significant cross-border wildlife crimes or pollution incidents were reported. However, isolated cases, such as the illegal killing of a brown bear that crossed into Austria, were mentioned.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: The interviewee said that poaching happens in the PNPG but is very limited.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The interviewee said that some episodes of poaching happened in the PNPG, but not for economic reasons. The damage was more to the image of the park, of impacting a sacred natural site. These episodes entail disrespecting laws, your territory, the people that think that animals should not be killed. The reason behind these episodes is cultural rather than economic. The park became a civil party and spent a lot of money, but the perpetrators were absolved and boast even today for this result. The consequence is more in terms of social and ethical damage than environmental. In the future, the Park Management Board may decide to not intervene on poaching to avoid spending money.

Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI: The interviewee said that fauna and habitats are very well monitored by inspectors and rangers, and therefore the level of control is so high that it does not allow for illegal activities.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: The interviewee mentioned small-scale wildlife crimes, such as poaching and species collection, as occasional issues.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: While the interviewee did not report direct biodiversity loss within the TNP, they acknowledged that Slovenia acts as a transit zone for wildlife crimes, particularly involving protected species. These activities typically occur outside protected areas, highlighting the need for better monitoring and enforcement mechanisms.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: The interviewee said that these phenomena are minimal, and that in the past illegal killing episodes were stopped thanks to the help of hunters that have immediately identified the transgressors.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee mentioned cases of wildlife crime such as Italian citizens hunting protected bird species in Slovenia, particularly in the Karst region, and illegal trapping of protected insect species in the Julian Alps.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: The interviewee mentioned an imbalanced wildlife population that results in an overabundance of deer and wolves, that disrupt the local ecosystem and hinder agriculture and sheep farming.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee noted that while there are no reported instances of wildlife crime in the TNP, increasing tourism pressure on ecosystems raises concerns about long-term sustainability.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: Illegal hunting was highlighted for bears and capercaillies. The interviewee explained that discrepancies in species protection laws (like the case of the capercaillie) across borders create enforcement challenges and lead to problematic situations as one species can be protected in one country and not in another or declared as foreign species and thus subject to hunting in one side on the border but not on the other.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: Currently the interviewee is not aware of wildlife crimes but mentioned that limited poaching episodes happened in the past and were tackled by the PNPG with legal actions.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: When asked about crimes in general, the interviewee said that there are no relevant phenomena in the area, at least when it comes to the Italian side that is the one the interviewee knows.

Were any air, soil, or water pollution directly contributing to habitat loss or degradation and a cross-border impact, identified? What were the tools and/or mechanisms identified, which would address these activities, if existent?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: The problem of overtourism and the creation of quiet zones was mentioned again in this context.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: Air, soil or water pollution is an irrelevant issue in the area.

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: The interviewee does not have any knowledge of this kind of crime in the Julian Alps but mentioned the case of the transboundary park Scarpe-Escaut between Belgium and France. On the French side, a company producing sugar had leaks that impacted a transboundary river, affecting the Belgian side of the park. While the company was condemned to restoration measures on the French side, nothing could be done for the Belgian side despite the damages. Although the interviewee was not aware of the precise development, it was mentioned that a process to ensure restoration on the Belgian side was initiated thanks to the presence of the transboundary park and the B-Solutions of the European Commission was involved.

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: The interviewee highlights that negative impacts on nature and biodiversity may come also from the deregulation of impact assessment procedures promoted by the EU to accelerate the transition to renewable energy sources (RES). This applies for instance to small hydroelectric factories.

On this matter there is also a conflict between the new EU framework that weakens requirement on environmental impact assessment (EIA) and the Energy Protocol of the Alpine Convention, which has more stringent requirement. This is an issue because the EU ratified this protocol, although the EU has established that EU Member States are free to adopt or maintain more stringent rules.

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: When questioned about potential episodes of pollution in Alpine protected areas, the interviewee answered that the Alpine Biodiversity Board will work on light pollution in the next mandate.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: Activities within the protected areas are limited and they do not have impact in terms of pollution. The issue in the park is abandonment rather than overexploitation of resources.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: Tourism-related activities, such as illegal driving in natural areas and high human presence, were identified as ongoing threats to biodiversity.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: The interviewee said that episodes of soil and water pollution happened in the TNP in an area bordering the PNPG, where a chemical plant operates close to the Soča-Isonzo river and poured chemical products within the river with consistent damages. The interviewee recalled an episode in 2023, but this was not the first and only time. Luckily pollution cannot occur easily in the PNPG, since the park extends over a more isolated area and there are no inhabited settlements except for two shepherd's cottages, *Malga Coot* and *Malga Cofin*, and the Summer village of *Sella Carnizza*. According to the interviewee the PNPG is preserved by episodes of pollution thanks to its isolated location: a decision that was driven by the lobbies of hunters and farmers that wanted the PNPG far from valleys. Instead, the TNP is much bigger, but is also endowed with a wide network of rangers to control the area and lately focuses on excessive/unsustainable tourism (*turismo selvaggio*).

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The interviewee said there are no problems with pollution in the PNPG. Traffic does not have an impact, and the Region FVG invested in ecological connectivity to facilitate the movements of animals.

Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI: No large-scale pollution in the area. What the interview can relate to this question is that sometimes factories may set on fire, and this causes emissions, but it is not a widespread phenomenon.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: The interviewee highlighted illegal driving and increased human presence in sensitive areas, which disturb habitats and species as one of the main concerns. Pollution is another critical issue, particularly in areas with heavy tourism activity in the TNP area.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: Minimal impact of agriculture due to the size and structure of this sector in the area. Quite on the contrary, the benefits of agriculture are higher than its negative impacts. The interviewee cited ecomafia and the illegal trade of toxic waste as problems for FVG, since it is a region that acts as a bridge for countries in Eastern Europe. But, as far as the interviewee knows, these phenomena do not concern the areas of the parks.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee mentioned inadequate wastewater management systems. Rivers are contaminated by untreated wastewater due to the inability of infrastructure to handle the influx of visitors during peak seasons. Tourism-related activities, such as mass events (e.g., concerts in fragile ecosystems like Lago di Fusine), were criticized for causing ecological harm, including habitat destruction and pollution.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: The interviewee mentioned water pollution, resulting from inadequate sewage systems in tourist accommodations.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: Specific issues mentioned include water pollution from inadequate sewage systems in the municipality and pollution from alpine huts in sensitive areas like the Seven Lakes Valley. These challenges are exacerbated during peak tourist seasons.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The interviewee mentioned water pollution as a one of the concerning issues linked to inadequate sewage systems in mountain touristic areas.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: Pollution is not a challenge in the PNPG area which benefits from a wild and authentic environment.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: The interviewee lamented the delay from public authorities to react to climate change, since they continue to invest in new skiing facilities and related touristic facilities linked to snow at very low heights. These projects have impacts on forest habitats for instance and the species that live there that are forced to move, and their reproduction cycle is therefore affected.

2.6 Information on evaluation to gather insights on the effectiveness of cooperation for transboundary conservation

Were the interviewees aware of any tools/mechanisms/procedures to evaluate the effectiveness of transboundary biodiversity conservation and, if used, how do evaluation reports contribute to the enhancement of transboundary biodiversity conservation, according to their perception/knowledge?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: Effectiveness is measured in the context of the periodic evaluation done for the EUROPARC certifications (Transboundary Park and ECST). For this the TNP and the PNPG need to jointly produce reports, and EUROPARC evaluators are coming to the field to verify the conditions. In Slovenia, they also have a management plan report that is due every 2 years and measures the progress with respect to their goals. Their management plan lasts for 10 years (they are currently elaborating the new one). There are also annual plans for which they have to report every 6 months to the competent ministries.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The Annual Forum is an event where local stakeholders evaluate the activities carried out.³⁴ The Steering Group among the parks also does an internal evaluation of their initiatives: During each meeting, the parks assess the level of implementation of planned activities and discuss difficulties. Finally, EUROPARC prepares every 5 years an evaluation report to confirm the certifications on the basis of the Action Plan for the Transboundary Ecoregion Julian Alps. An indirect evaluation of the

³⁴ As far as we could observe by participating in these events (once in presence and the other time online), participants are free to express their views on everything that was presented and even outside the scope of the official agenda of the Annual Forum. However, discussions on the evaluation of individual measures in not carried out systematically, and the happy/unhappy emoticons are assigned to planned or implemented measures by the parks.

effectiveness of their actions in terms of ecological connectivity is the fact that the parks are invited as partners of EU projects on this topic, for example Dinalpconnect and AlpBionet.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: Within the Steering Group an empirical evaluation is performed on the actions carried out, but the interviewee would appreciate having a biodiversity evaluation system based on a set of objective indicators and criteria. For instance, the evaluation performed by EUROPARC is mostly subjective since it is based on few elements and few codified indicators.

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: The interviewee explained that the method to evaluate effectiveness was elaborated by EUROPARC some time ago and considers IUCN criteria. The EUROPARC method includes a set of standards referring to specific indicators, which are qualitative more than quantitative. EUROPARC provides protected areas interested in achieving transboundary park recognition with a manual to have a check list and verify the status of the cooperation process. There are institutional standards (if there are documents formalizing cooperation, memorandum of understanding, management plan, etc.), standards relating to the purposes of cooperation (*in primis* conservation, then tourism, etc.), and the involvement of local communities. Based on this method, the parks can do an auto-evaluation and understand their weaknesses and send a report to EUROPARC. Once the parks present an application form, EUROPARC sends an evaluator on the field to verify but above all to suggest and support the parks in their cooperation process, to improve the functioning of protected areas. Once the evaluator drafts the report, a Commission of experts evaluates it and provides recommendations, which are then approved by the EUROPARC Council. The effectiveness of cooperation is impacted by changes, political tensions, or if the cooperation process was initiated on the basis of a project (like those funded by Interreg) that is going to finish and the person in charge will not be renewed. The interviewee reflected on what can happen in terms of effectiveness on biodiversity conservation if cooperation ends. Much depends on how cooperation was structured, the arrangements behind it, the focus of the work, the motivation for cooperating. Usually, protected areas continue working autonomously, but the quality of some initiatives, the collection of data, or decisions taken can have a different quality.

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: When asked about effectiveness, the interviewee responded as follows. The motto of the Italian Presidency of the Alpine Convention is “Work it out!”. In line with this, the interviewee thinks that the only way to obtain good results is to work together and cooperate. The interviewee aims to concretize this vision in the Action Plan on Alpine Biodiversity to be developed during the Italian Presidency. This plan should contain the main organizational and financial aspects that are instrumental for ensuring the protection of mountainous biodiversity. The interviewee also thinks that an important aspect of biodiversity protection is the creation of buffer zones (*aree attigue*). An explicit engagement of States on this topic would be fundamental, and the Italian Presidency is pushing towards that. The interviewee imagines something similar to the river contract (*contratti di fiume*) to be applied to ecological corridors, what they define by coining a new term as transboundary ecological corridor contracts.

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: The aspect of evaluation of transboundary conservation indirectly emerged when talking about the pilot region for ecological connectivity; nevertheless, the interview did not reflect on this point, but referred to the document “Ecological network in the Alps: defining criteria and objectives for pilot region”,³⁵ which could contain useful insights.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: Due to an infringement procedure initiated in 2015, the EU Commission asked IT, and thus all Italian regions, to define conservation objectives for species and habitats of Natura 2000

³⁵ CIPRA International (2009) Final Report *Ecological network in the Alps: defining criteria and objectives for pilot region*, available at https://www.alpconv.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Fotos/Banner/Organisation/thematic_working_bodies/Part_01/ecological_network_platform/9_Pilotregionen_e-2.pdf

sites, since the approach previously adopted was generic. Now, there is a clearer approach: to define a conservation objective entails defining in quantitative or qualitative terms, with clear indicators, which is the objective of conservation; hence, the conservation status to be reached for a single species or habitat at a certain date. FVG approved these objectives and, based on that, Natura 2000 conservation measures will be updated. This approach will ensure an effective system able to measure the improvement in terms of biodiversity and of the status of all species and habitats of Annexes I and II of the Habitats Directive. In addition, there are the semestral report of the Habitats and Birds Directives on the conservation status at regional level; therefore, the monitoring has to be extended to the whole regional territory. The level of details required by the EU Commission is more precise, which is leading towards a real quantification of the conservation status and evolution. It emerged that ensuring adequate funding is important to guarantee effective biodiversity conservation and evaluate the effectiveness of the action: money is needed to ensure monitoring, financing improvement measures, etc. The crucial issue is having a constant monitoring system that monitors all, or almost all, species or at least use umbrella species to understand the evolution of some populations. Therefore, there should be a circuit that links environmental pressures on conservation and conservation measures that block these pressures, and all should be verified through monitoring in order to close the circle. Furthermore, according to the interviewee, cooperation on the protection of species and habitat is enhanced by the obligations contained in EU Directives. When, for instance, evaluating the environmental impact of a project or drafting conservation measures for a Natura 2000 site, the reference point is the presence of that habitat or that species at European level and the role of every Region, every State in the wider European framework.

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI: The achievement of the objectives included in the candidature of the UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserve will be evaluated by UNESCO within 10 years from the recognition. The positive side of this evaluation is its flexibility: if within these 10 years new needs emerge, the Biosphere Reserve may add new objectives without having to notify UNESCO of the change. Only during the 10-year monitoring process, the Reserve will have to justify its choice to add new objectives and actions. On whether in their experience it is thanks to the existence of these Reserves that sustainable development is advancing, they said that this correlation cannot be demonstrated because external changes also contribute to influence the effectiveness of reaching out the planned objectives. The instrument of the MAB Biosphere Reserve however is very effective in attracting external funds.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: Evaluation of transboundary cooperation is limited. While international agreements and bilateral projects include reporting obligations, there is no standardized mechanism for regular evaluation. Differences in monitoring approaches between countries further complicate efforts to assess conservation outcomes at the transboundary level. Recent EU-funded projects aim to address these gaps by standardizing monitoring methods.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: According to the interviewee transboundary cooperation is effective in terms of biodiversity conservation results, more than in other sectors, like tourism, which requires further work. However, there is the fear that cooperation on conservation issues is too dependent on EU funds (LIFE, Interreg) and when these funds are missing, there are gaps in terms of biodiversity monitoring and conservation. The presence of the transboundary Steering Group is a strength since it ensures daily communication and effective collaboration.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The interviewee spoke about biodiversity conservation in the PNPG and highlighted that there are no big issues since this is the task performed by the park and the objective is maintaining the area as it is. There are important measures for endemic species (like the rock partridge - *coturnice*) and habitats that are giving good results. It was also said that the PNPG Management Board gives directives and must monitor if at the operational level these directives are followed. The interviewee

praised the work of the current PNPG Director, a “tractor” that loves the job and works tirelessly. One of the engines of these good results is that the Director has the same vision as local administrators. Moreover, most of the PNPG staff are also local people (from Resia), know directly the issues addressed, and possess the cultural, traditional and linguistic sensitivities characteristic of this area. The interviewee added that cooperation between the PNPG and the TNP works well, an example was that over ibex. It was highlighted that the TNP has several internal organizations/associations and the PNPG is in contact with all of them. The PNPG keeps the TNP informed of all its initiatives and aims to involve the TNP, for instance in the project proposal within the Italian branch of Alparc. At the Alpine level the PNPG and TNP are seen as “brothers”, this is also thanks to the very good relationship between the staff of the two parks. In addition, it was highlighted the importance to adopt a transboundary MAB approach in all initiatives that had a national dimension before.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: Effectiveness of biodiversity conservation is evaluated primarily through mandatory EU reporting on the state of habitats and species, particularly in Natura 2000 areas. Additionally, specific conservation programs, often funded by LIFE projects, provide data on targeted species and habitats. The interviewee suggested using indicator species to monitor the success of conservation measures and transboundary initiatives.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: Transboundary cooperation can be evaluated through criteria like the number of joint projects, the range of stakeholders involved (number of stakeholders involved), what kind of topics and how many topics stakeholders work together, as well as financial (what is the financial input from the states to support the transboundary cooperation) and human resource commitments (from the parks, from projects, from the local level). Capacity issues were also mentioned as there could be interest in a certain topic, but they struggle to find the necessary financial or human resources. The interviewee suggested that EGTCs could provide a practical framework for evaluation by aligning regional goals and facilitating measurable outcomes.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: The interviewee cited the lack of institutional cooperation as an element useful for evaluation.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: According to this interviewee, a measure of effectiveness of transboundary cooperation should be to have similar standards (for example on hunting practices) across borders.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee lacked detailed knowledge about specific tools, mechanisms, or formal procedures explicitly designed to evaluate the effectiveness of transboundary biodiversity conservation.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: Transboundary conservation efforts were perceived by the interviewee as somewhat effective, particularly where the management of wildlife (e.g., wolves and deer) required coordination. However, they stressed that these efforts need synchronization across countries to be impactful. Overall, there was a sense that the cooperation mechanism relied on operational, not strategic alignment, focusing on immediate ecological issues rather than systemic collaboration. They highlighted the importance of TNP employees understanding residents' needs for effective action, as direct involvement of farms in councils or organizations was sporadic. However, the interviewee was unaware of specific tools or procedures for evaluating transboundary biodiversity conservation. They criticized the lack of studies on the economic and social impacts of conservation policies, emphasizing the need for better data to guide decisions.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee did not provide detailed insights into evaluation mechanisms for transboundary cooperation. However, they suggested that success could be measured by the effectiveness of joint tourism products, changes in visitor flows, and the integration of cross-border collaboration into regional planning.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: Monitoring of Natura 2000 species and habitats forms the primary evaluation mechanism. However, this focus on European-priority species leaves gaps in broader biodiversity monitoring. Lack of state resources further limits comprehensive evaluations. The interviewee highlighted how Natura 2000's implementation in Slovenia overshadowed other conservation priorities, calling for broader focus beyond EU-mandated areas. They also emphasized the role of local actors in shaping conservation outcomes and the importance of adapting strategies to each country's unique context.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: The interviewee said that cooperation is effective and the meetings of the PNPG Management Board are useful for local administrators to be informed by the park staff about the situation in the area and all the initiatives involving the park.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: The interviewee evaluated positively the capacity of transboundary cooperation, which derives from a strong initiative of the PNPG and of particular persons promoting this transboundary vision. The interviewee mentioned that specific projects have a system of monitoring and monitoring duties embedded in them. Therefore, evaluation is mostly project specific. In the interviewee's opinion, what would be needed is the development of meta-indicators that go beyond specific projects and have a transboundary character. Their association is doing something similar to evaluate the cooperation existing between Gorizia and Nova Gorica, which they consider a unified urban system since the distance between these municipalities is of only 3 km².

2.7 Information on paths to future development

What were the interviewees' hopes for transboundary biodiversity conservation in the area, and, according to their view, what kind of new participatory tools, institutional structures, as well as funding and evaluation mechanisms would be required to realize these? What would be the benefits of these new tools, structures or mechanisms?

Did the interviewees share some thoughts on realistic future prospects for transboundary biodiversity conservation efforts?

Int_JulianAlps_01_PM_SI: Their vision is to create a trilateral MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. Their wish is to keep the connections they have established over the years and to improve the engagement with local stakeholders and entities that work on nature conservation on both sides of the border. The core of the cooperation, however, will remain the parks. The Julian Alps as a unified territory is seen as a way to cooperate on tourism and to exchange practices in the monitoring of species. They do not wish for new institutions to be created, because this would cause people's disengagement. What is needed are concrete results to persuade people of the importance of cooperation. To realize this vision, they would probably need additional personnel to be acquired for instance through projects.

Int_JulianAlps_02_PM_IT: The main vision is related to the recognition of the Julian Alps as a unified area without distinguishing between Italy and Slovenia. The realization of this vision could bring enormous benefits for their small realities unifying their forces to count more and to promote the development of

their territory. They intend to capitalize on the common brand Julian Alps. This vision is linked to the recognition of the Julian Alps as a UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. From a more operational point of view, the parks would like to institutionalize annual thematic tables, where stakeholders from both countries could come together and discuss their common problems. One thing the parks discussed in depth is how to finance the Transboundary Reserve. In this sense, they will continue to use their own funds to finance the cooperation and to take shifts in financing common activities. However, the issue of funding remains open. They know realities that share personnel and what they would like to achieve is to have people that are financed to work on transboundary cooperation. These funds should come in view of the interviewee from the respective States and should serve at least to finance the functioning of the coordination body of the Transboundary Reserve. So funding is a strategic sector for the future of the area. Strategic for future development is also youth.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: According to the interviewee the transboundary dimension should be valued since it can offer the opportunity to experiment with management methods broadly speaking, as well as biodiversity co-management, that in other [non-transboundary, ed.] areas can become more complex. The interviewee clearly stated the interest in making the PNPG a pilot area to test evaluation indicators in detail and improve them after the experimentation. From a more operational perspective, a profile that should be introduced to support cooperation is that of “territorial animators”: personnel that knows both languages (Italian and Slovenian) and work at local level by both explaining what the parks do and gathering the needs of territorial actors. Young people would be well suited for such a role. Moreover, the interviewee expressed the wish to have transboundary staff shared between the parks and mentioned that within the two parks they reasoned on what transboundary staff means and entails, since the perception of what transboundary is depends on how far you leave from the border. It would be very useful to join the forest corps of both parks for transboundary patrolling for biodiversity conservation purposes. Another wish/expectation is linked to the identification of a unique management entity for close Natura 2000 sites and the development of a unique management plan; for instance, this would be ideal in the Canin area, and this proposal could be submitted to the EU Commission “B-solution” initiative.

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: According to interviewee, transboundary and regional cooperation is the most effective way to work and, more generally, live. Transboundary biodiversity cooperation enhances European cooperation and strengthens it and thus can influence politics. In this context, local and regional peculiarities are preserved, but through international cooperation the supranational interest prevails over the national one. In addition, transboundary biodiversity cooperation contributes to peace: thanks to the technical work people can dialogue and overcome political issues; once people know each other and work together, collaborating is easier, and conflicts can be prevented. Good policy work at all levels would be beneficial to make politicians aware of the benefits of transboundary cooperation. Targeted communication is essential: adapting the message and way of communicating to the audience (a mayor, a MEP, a Commissioner). Moreover, information should not be taken for granted since the target audience does not have the knowledge of experts. MEPs deal with so many things that need to be briefed and prepared to decide. Informing politicians and decision-makers is a complex process and requires multiple actions, there is not a unique strategic solution. For instance, identifying MEPs coming from areas where transboundary cooperation is in place, so that the park or territorial actors contact the politician, who gets interested to gain more votes. Then, EUROPARC contacts the same politician to raise attention on the cooperation process. This is not lobbying but making them aware of the situation in different ways. It is also important to select the right people to contact, especially at the local level, to see if there are synergies on the topics tackled and present the issue in connection with the interests of these people. Messages must be extremely targeted both on the single person and the party this person belongs to.

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: The EU Nature Restoration Law will be useful for the articulation of national restoration plans since they will have all the same format and facilitate cooperation between Alpine

countries to pursue restoration objectives, even if there is no reference to transnational aspects. Another objective pursued within the Alpine Convention is the inclusion of Alpine ecological connectivity in spatial planning documents. The interviewee also mentioned that monitoring systems are not harmonized and there are no indicators for the Alps: The AlpsLife project aims to address this issue and identify common indicators to monitor Alpine biodiversity and foster cooperation.

Int_JulianAlps_07_RA_IT: The interviewee stressed the importance to capitalize on and give continuity to old projects, especially small ones. In this respect, the interviewee mentioned the example of a project database in the INTERREG IT-AT. In the view of the interviewee, finding the right balance between conservation and human needs is key. For instance, find a balance between grazing activities that are economically sustainable and conservation of meadows areas; finding a balance between the need for renewable energy through hydropower and its impact on conservation. An important project is creating a regional ecological network by working on both internal and external connectivity, so with territories of other States. So creating a connectivity network on areas that have a lower naturalistic value but ensure a medium level and spread connectivity across wider areas. To this end, specific measures are included in the Common Agricultural Policy to target the agricultural sector: to maintain meadows and natural environments, wetland conservation, etc. Funds are foreseen, but there is reluctance to use them. In the future, the approach of farmer should change as well and they should see themselves as landscape restorer, this might be a future profession. According to the interviewee the protected areas management system has reached good result, but it is important to avoid maintaining them isolated from each other. Active biodiversity conservation is crucial. Another important process would be to work on the alignment of national legal frameworks to facilitate a joint management of biodiversity beyond cooperation ensured through projects.

Int_JulianAlps_09_PM_SI: The representatives expressed hope for enhanced cooperation frameworks, emphasizing the need for harmonized legislation, improved monitoring systems, and sustainable funding mechanisms. They envisioned a unified approach to data collection and analysis, supported by strong institutional frameworks and ongoing knowledge exchange. However, they acknowledged that resistance to aligning national policies and practices remains a significant barrier. Despite these obstacles, the interviewees remained optimistic about the potential for improved cooperation through persistent efforts and incremental progress.

Int_JulianAlps_10_Y_IT: The interviewee wishes the identification of funds dedicated to biodiversity conservation and habitat restoration that are continuous and homogenous. This objective requires the commitment of protected areas in looking for such funds and drafting EU projects to ensure continuity in terms of research. Since the PNPG is a small park with a small permanent staff (10 people), the presence of these funds is crucial to hire external experts and researchers to ensure data collection on a long-term basis. This objective should be clear for the managers of this wide transboundary area. Creating new participatory instruments is also seen as crucial. For instance, the ECTS Annual forum is a good example. Young people could have a primary role in the development of participatory tools since there is the need to overcome traditional formats like a classic conference and learn how to use new available instruments. The interviewee works in Erasmus projects that foresee non-formal education techniques (e.g. working groups, fora, field visits, and case studies) that could be used to increase participation. Young people are more used to these new formats. Therefore, the interviewee wishes the creation of new participatory instruments, the involvement of local communities, local associations, and all relevant territorial actors to gather new visions, tools, and proposals especially those coming from youth. The interviewee had already shared the importance of being involved in European and conservation networks and the value of lessons learnt in those contexts.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: One of the hopes is the availability of additional funds for municipalities located within MAB areas and parks. These funds should be provided by the Ministry of Environment as well as in the context of Federparchi. In this regard, the interviewee highlighted that a lot of money foreseen for Italian national parks cannot be spent due to the rigid financial rules imposed by the Ministry; therefore, part of these resources could be reallocated in favor of MAB areas [this is already the case according to **Int_JulianAlps_08_OI**, ed.] or regional parks. The availability of funds for municipalities in MAB areas would make mayors keener to be part of such an area. The interviewee talked about cooperation with both AT and SI and the wish that the transboundary process embraces the three States (IT, SI, and AT) since the Julian Alps area and the inhabitants have a transboundary DNA. Another wish (and challenge) is to change the cultural mindset of those living within the area to fully understand the value and potential of a UNESCO MAB Reserve. If citizens are aware of this value and transfer this will to their political representatives, all the rest (financial resources, projects) comes naturally. As the interviewee said: “It is less difficult to preserve the ibex, the chamois, than to preserve minds or open minds”.

Int_JulianAlps_12_NA_SI: The interviewee’s hope is that transboundary cooperation projects are not discontinued over time also to capitalize on the know-how built through projects. Between projects there should be some form of cooperation not to have gaps, to be financed by the national level or the EU.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: The interviewee expressed hope for strengthened transboundary cooperation, particularly through bottom-up initiatives supported by national and regional actors. They emphasized the importance of aligning legislation between countries, as differing regulations often hinder joint efforts. Additional funding, improved institutional structures, and harmonized legal frameworks were identified as key steps to enhance cooperation. The interviewee also stressed the need for shared strategies to manage tourism sustainably and address environmental pressures.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: The interviewee expressed hopes for transboundary cooperation to strengthen biodiversity conservation while supporting local development, offering ecological agriculture and sustainable tourism as models for the future. They emphasized the need for integrated spatial planning and ecological agriculture as tools for sustainable prosperity in remote areas. Key requirements include better funding mechanisms, enhanced legislative harmonization, and stronger collaboration with local stakeholders to demonstrate the economic and social benefits of conservation.

Int_JulianAlps_15_ES_IT: The interviewee cited further extending the MAB Reserve to more remote areas, while responding to another question. When asked about their vision for conservation and the role of agriculture, the interviewee indicated simplification/streamlining (*semplificare*) as the main strategy. Also, more participation on concrete issues (less on strategies) is what the interviewee hopes for. Awareness raising is also fundamental. The interviewee recognizes however that involving entrepreneurs is extremely difficult.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: In the interviewee’s view, to realize the necessary changes, there should be legislative reforms to uniform the standards on hunting and wildlife management across borders. In some other cases, it would be sufficient to implement the agreements from the 1970s that Federaccia, a hunting association, concluded with the approval of the region FVG with Slovenian ministries responsible for hunting. These agreements aimed to implement a joint monitoring of fauna and a joint plan of legal killing of specimens. Equilibrium and rationality would be needed when it comes to the balancing of interests between environmentalists and hunters.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee emphasized the need for greater cooperation between Slovenian and Italian stakeholders, particularly in aligning efforts in spatial planning, biodiversity

protection, and sustainable development. Interest was expressed in more integrated projects that involve both countries, citing potential joint initiatives such as improving access for disabled individuals in mountainous areas and promoting shared heritage interpretation on the TNP area in connection to the Peace Park initiative. The interviewee also hoped for greater involvement of NGOs in planning and decision-making processes, emphasizing their ability to act as mediators and provide expert input. A future where biodiversity conservation is prioritized as a shared responsibility, with better monitoring, enforcement, and resource allocation across borders was presented as the main hope.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: The interviewee expressed hopes for balanced land management that preserves biodiversity while supporting agriculture. They advocated for integrated land use by creating buffer zones with mixed-use forest and pasture areas. The interviewee viewed systemic changes, such as reducing agricultural land loss and managing wolf populations, as critical for the long-term success of conservation efforts. Addressing gaps in knowledge about socio-economic impacts with improved data and studies was also mentioned. Finally, the need for critical, innovative thinking among young farmers to address future challenges was also highlighted.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee's vision for transboundary biodiversity conservation focuses on achieving a balance between tourism development and nature preservation. They emphasized the importance of local involvement and sustainable practices, using a "living room" metaphor to illustrate the need for guests (tourists) to respect the host's (locals') space and rules. To realize these hopes, the interviewee advocated for greater integration between tourism and conservation sectors, enhanced funding mechanisms, and the development of cross-border tourism products that align with conservation goals.

Int_JulianAlps_20_NA_SI: The interviewee's hopes included finding a balance between tourism and conservation, reducing numbers of tourists, and aiming at higher quality tourism. They called for new tools such as permanent funding using, for example, tourism revenues. Improved coordination between ministries and across borders was also mentioned highlighting the importance to have comparable institutional bodies, comparable for instance to the Institute for Nature Conservation in Slovenia, in the two countries as both countries have different systems, face different situations, and have different goals. Stakeholder engagement with enhanced participatory frameworks involving civil society and economic sectors was also mentioned by the interviewee. These would ensure sustainable biodiversity conservation and align cross-border objectives.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: A medium-long term objective is to understand the financial opportunities linked to the MAB Reserve and fully understand the mechanisms to access and take advantage of them. The governance mechanism of the MAB Reserve should support in achieving the aforementioned objective by sharing the knowledge and working method with the staff of municipalities, to ensure that financial resources are fully accessed and used. An example of a concrete project that will benefit the area is the school in the park, the school of the Julian Alps UNESCO MAB Reserve, which is currently under construction. The school will include pupils from the kindergarten to the lower secondary school, and the didactical programs offered will include components dedicated to the protected area and the MAB Reserve to make pupils and their families aware of the local heritage and able to safeguard and transmit these values. The educational program is being developed together with the University of Udine. The visions of the interviewee are connected to concrete opportunities linked to the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve in terms of accessing financial resources and realizing actions that benefit territorial actors to maintain local communities alive, help people to stay in mountain areas, and protect them.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: The interviewee said that transboundary cooperation necessitates the active involvement of local stakeholders. This is true also for the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve that otherwise would remain empty letter. For this to happen, probably new modalities of participation need to be experimented. When asked explicitly, the interviewee agreed that the thematic coordination tables foreseen in the MAB Reserve candidature could be a good way to improve this aspect. The interviewee also mentioned the development of transboundary indicators that go beyond projects to measure the effectiveness of transboundary cooperation. A way to improve involvement is in the interviewee's opinion to restart the dialogue on the Transboundary Peace Park.

2.8 Additional relevant information gathered during the interviews

Were there any additional (case-specific) questions asked during the interview? Did they reveal relevant aspects of the cooperation and communication between the stakeholders, affecting transboundary biodiversity conservation in the area?

Any other relevant information or findings from the interview, which wasn't covered by the questions above might be included here.

Examples of specific questions were the following (not exhaustive list):

- How does the Alpine Convention contribute to biodiversity and nature conservation (Protocol and Alpine Biodiversity Board)?
- To what extent can the Alpine Convention support cooperation for transboundary biodiversity conservation? In this framework, is it possible to discuss the harmonization of national legislations?
- To what extent the creation of Alparc has been contributing to the transboundary conservation of biodiversity and ecological connectivity?
- Based on which criteria is the recognition of the Transboundary pilot region for ecological connectivity recognized by the Alpine Convention? Is there a periodical check of the pilot sites to verify their ecological status? If yes, based on which criteria?
- Through what initiatives does the Slovenian Ministry of Natural Resources and Spatial Planning promote transboundary biodiversity conservation (in particular in the case of the Julian Alps MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve)?
- How could transboundary biodiversity conservation be pursued in the case of neighboring Natura 2000 sites? Is the Ministry working on any dossier in this regard, including in the European context?
- Is EUSALP contributing to the protection of biodiversity at transboundary level? If yes, in which ways?
- What does it mean for an association/body/municipality like yours collaborating with a park? How does this cooperation concretize?

- Were you or your organization involved in the preparation process of the candidature to become a UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve? If yes, which actions did you suggest to be included in the Reserve's Action Plan?
- Do you have direct relations with the associations/bodies like yours on the other side of the border?
- When did the involvement of youth started in the context of the PNPG? What is the role of the Youth Council (YC)?
- Are there direct benefits for youth deriving from transboundary cooperation in the field of biodiversity conservation?
- Through which initiatives does the Region FVG promote the protection of biodiversity also at transboundary level? What is the role of the region in the implementation of the Habitats and Birds Directives? Does the region make available funds to promote (transboundary) biodiversity protection? What role does the region play in evaluating the effectiveness of biodiversity conservation measures?

In most cases rather than asking completely new questions, we adapted the scope of the common questionnaire. The additional pieces of information reported below did not necessarily result from asking the specific questions listed, but rather from digressions made by the interviewees spontaneously or from follow-up questions that emerged during the interview.

Int_JulianAlps_03_PM_IT: The interviewee underlined the importance of involving youth (especially those between 18 and 30) living in the protected areas. They described the efforts done by the PNPG to this end through different initiatives, ranging from the Junior Rangers Program to the creation of the PNPG Youth Council (YC), which has become the YC of the national Julian Alps Biosphere Reserve as well. The YC carries out activities throughout the year: for instance, they organize a film festival dedicated to nature, mountain, and the environment. Another yearly activity is "Nature Beats": a day with concerts, workshops on environmental topics, and other activities in all the territories of the park. They organize "Youth at the top", which is an event promoted by Alparc to raise awareness of young people on mountain areas. This active involvement of youth in the PNPG is a good practice that has been taken as an example in Italy and Europe. One of the YC representatives of the PNPG joined the EUROPARC Managing Board as youth representative. Since the interviewee also sits in the EUROPARC Managing Board, it was highlighted that it is the first time in the history of EUROPARC that two delegates belong to the same park. Moreover, a representative from the PNPG YC is also a representative a youth within EUROPARC as well. The creation of a YC is also foreseen in the governance of the Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve. Moreover, the PNPG YC spurred a normative reform in the FVG regional park law: A young representative indicated by the mayors joins the Park Management Board as a component. On the Slovenian side, youth involvement is lower and there is the hope to advance on this aspect as well.

Int_JulianAlps_04_IO: Regarding the elements that enhance transboundary cooperation, and the actors involved, due to the working experience on several cooperation projects, the interviewee stated that the more actors are involved at different levels, the more cooperation is effective. The people involved in cooperation need to have the heart and be the engine: If people involved are passionate about the cooperation project, it works. This individual psychological component can be both a strength and a weakness. Often the Directors of protected areas are key in cooperation thanks to their awareness/sensitivity (*sensibilità*), interest, and international approach. Some people are naturally interested in understanding what happens across the border for cultural, psychological, and linguistic reasons. Therefore, depending on the people involved, cooperation starts and evolves or gets hindered.

According to the experience of the interviewee, once the Director of the park is interested, several mechanisms are put in place and the staff gets involved. In some other cases the staff of the parks have been collaborating for some time and involve a new director as well. If the latter gets passionate thanks to the individual characteristics already mentioned, cooperation continues, otherwise, it can be limited. Cooperation is an additional task to what the director/staff has to do. Therefore, if the cooperation approach belongs to the *modus operandi* of the director/staff and is seen as an additional value, then financial and motivational resources are invested in the cooperation effort; otherwise, it becomes another burdensome task on the desk. Therefore, the first and crucial actors in the transboundary cooperation between protected areas are Directors and then, consequently, their staff. In some cases, the Directors are interested in cooperation, but delegate to another person from their staff who becomes responsible for cooperation. Here the risk is that the cooperation project becomes a task of this person. On the one hand, one of the pros is the identification of one interlocutor who could be proficient in both languages – in the case of cooperation between parks belonging to two different States. On the other hand, it can be a weakness if cooperation is limited to this person. In addition to the Directors and their staff, the other actors to be involved are at both a higher and a lower level. For instance, local communities must be involved, there can be local associations, local municipalities working together through twinning agreements, transboundary farmer associations, etc. The more cooperation mechanisms exist, the stronger the cooperation process is; this entails that at cultural level there is a sense of transboundary community, the perception of common problems, and the will to find joint solutions. In this picture, history and geography are crucial. In terms of geography, there might be two parks divided by mountains where the passage is possible from spring on, otherwise, the connection between the two sides is very complicated. In other situations, borders are easy to cross and local communities may not perceive them as such since their families are spread across the borders, or people live in one country and work in the other. Therefore, geography has an impact on cooperation and impacts history as well, especially in Europe. In South Africa the topics of peace and transboundary cooperation is very important and quite sensitive since war can be forgotten only after three generations: the person who experienced war struggle to see the other as someone to cooperate rather than a previous enemy; the children are influenced by the history of their parents; while the grandchildren know that their grandparents experienced war, but things get blurred. If everything goes well, peace is stable, but there might be situations – like nowadays – which revive war brutally. Therefore, the difficulties of cooperating are not just a political issue, but affects people as well, due to the emergence of unsolved historical conflicts. At a higher institutional level, regions or States must support the cooperation process, or at least not hinder it. Based on what the interviewee gathered from the field, when political tensions between two States were higher, cooperation was more technical and less visible but did not end. For example, there were monitoring activities, informal meetings, a few initiatives, and projects. While governments were arguing, collaboration was maintained at local/territorial level. When the political situation was more positive, cooperation was more visible. Therefore, in some countries, cooperation has ups and downs depending on the political situation. With the war in Ukraine, the situation has got so bad that cooperation under the radar is not possible. The Finnish Government gave indications to cut completely relations with Russia at all levels, and thus cooperation on biodiversity ended as well. In this case, the role of national actors has been negative, and, in some cases, has affected personal and unofficial relations among Directors and staff of protected areas as well. So, cooperation between Finland and Russia has been compromised significantly with the war in Ukraine. At the beginning of the war, there was the perception that after a year cooperation would be revived, for instance in the case of Inari that was awarded the EUROPARC recognition. Finland and Norway asked for postponing the re-evaluation of one year, hoping that cooperation with Russia could be revived; in the meantime, cooperation between Finland and Norway was maintained. Unfortunately, the continuation of the war is compromising cooperation so much that the whole cooperation process with Russia needs to start all over again. Nevertheless, the interviewee did not know how the situation with the re-evaluation of the EUROPARC recognition in the Inari evolved precisely after changing the post. It was also mentioned that, in another case, probably the Paanajärvi,

cooperation between Finland and Russia was difficult for other circumstances (change of the Russian director and Russian conservation laws), but was ended the cooperation project indefinitely. Other actors that may influence the cooperation process in an indirect way are external donors, like the European Union. The political and financial support to transboundary cooperation enhances and spurs these processes. When talking about environmental pollution, the interviewee mentioned the role of the B-Solutions initiative of the European Commission in solving a case in the Scarpe-Escaut transboundary park. It was highlighted that the B-Solutions experts give (non-binding) legal advice on how to solve transboundary issues. When talking about the benefits of transboundary cooperation, the interviewee mentioned that legislative changes can be influenced by cooperation, especially within the European Union. In the view of the interviewee, politicians coming from bordering areas where cooperation exists can have an impact at national and European levels. For instance, this happened when working with a politician of the TNP area: They bring territorial issues in legislative contexts. Regarding the possibility to institutionally structure cooperation, the interviewee highlighted that institutionalizing cooperation can be a double-edged sword: on the one hand, it entails bureaucratizing processes, using complex mechanisms, etc.; on the other hand, it strengthens the process and, regardless of the will of a single person, makes cooperation more stable. Regarding the stratification of several recognition and conservation frameworks, the interviewee said that if the cooperative approach intrinsic to cooperation and transboundary recognition is embedded in the daily work and seen as an added value, then everything works. However, if obtaining a transboundary recognition/certification is simply an additional task, then there may be problems. For this reason, the interviewee underlined the importance of selecting the certification needed: a certification that is useful, that can support cooperation processes and results with more resources, in an easier and more effective way. In reality, these kinds of decisions are influenced by politics, and administrators choose to achieve a recognition for its nominal value rather than its real impact, without knowing the instruments available. A problem connected to the stratification of several mechanisms is their potential competition. These mechanisms entail a certain amount of work (filling an application form, verifying the criteria every X years, etc.), and thus the institutions granting them (like IUCN, UNESCO, EUROPARC) should collaborate and enhance mutual recognition of these processes by validating specific sections of the application procedures that have been already certified within another mechanism. The emergence of new instruments and methodologies can create difficulties. As part of the EUROPARC staff, the interviewee often received questions by applicants on the possibility to skip a certain recognition section due to possession of another recognition; for instance, this problem emerged even within EUROPARC between the ECST and transboundary cooperation recognition processes. The management authority of a protected areas should select the most appropriate recognition depending on the time and efforts needed; often the criteria guiding this selection are what gives more visibility, more financial resources, or a stronger support network.

Int_JulianAlps_05_NA_IT: This interviewee describes in some detail the ratification process of the Alpine Convention and its protocols, including the one on nature and landscape protection (pp. 8-9 of the transcript).

Int_JulianAlps_06_IO: The interviewee highlighted the importance of the Alpine Convention to strengthen policy cooperation around environmental issues that have a transboundary character, like river restoration. This Convention gives space to understand differences and aspirations of other countries, and to develop common tools. It furthermore guides and creates synergies of policy actions and, in this way, aims to overcome legislative barriers among countries. Regarding the Alpine Convention recognition of the Julian Alps as a transboundary pilot region for ecological connectivity, the interviewee

referred to the report “Ecological network in the Alps: defining criteria and objectives for pilot region”³⁶ for more information on the general criteria and the specific case. Moreover, it was made clear that there is no periodical review of this recognition, the initiative ended with the identification of pilot areas and the dedicated platform was closed. The thematic working group Spatial Planning and Sustainable Development is the successor of the ecological network platform.

Int_JulianAlps_08_OI: Based on their experience on assisting the PNPG and the TNP in the preparation of the candidature for the UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, the interviewee on our request described how this process was structured. They were appointed by both parks, as representatives of their national MAB Biosphere Reserves, to prepare the candidature. They always worked trilaterally on this dossier: the two parks and the interviewee’s organization. In the preparation of the candidature an essential part is to involve local stakeholders (see section 2.2 above). Becoming a Transboundary Biosphere Reserve is not a certification, but more a recognition that there is the willingness and the ambition in a given territory to cooperate to achieve over time certain objectives. When the Reserve is recognized, those objectives are not already fulfilled. What the Reserve “certifies” is that there are some common objectives that a number of subjects are willing to achieve together with a series of local stakeholders. The core of the candidature is a list of projects that aim to be put in place in a timeframe of 10 years. In 10 years, UNESCO will assess what projects have been carried out and whether objectives have been achieved. The Transboundary Reserve adds up to the 2 national Reserves that continue to exist in parallel.³⁷ The interviewee emphasized that there is nothing that the two parks would have not been able to do without this recognition, for instance organizing coordination tables or working together on projects, but the UNESCO Reserve is a powerful symbol and brand that stimulates cooperation in their experience. However, this enthusiasm needs to be cultivated to bring results, otherwise it fades away. This recognition is also very attractive vis-à-vis those actors that before the recognition was granted were not very keen to cooperate. When asked to compare the MAB Biosphere Reserve to the EGTC in terms of the incentives to cooperation it may give, the interviewee replied that they do not know the EGTC as an instrument of cooperation in the field of sustainable development. In contrast, UNESCO is a well-recognized “certification” and a unique selling point for involving external actors. Being a UNESCO MAB Biosphere Reserve, however, does not mean that the recognized site is unique. Uniqueness is only a characteristic of the UNESCO World Heritage program. The different phases of the candidature process were the following: 1) information (informing all relevant stakeholders of the willingness to obtain this recognition and of the different phases of the process); 2) involvement of relevant stakeholders (see section 2.2 above); 3) streamlining of what was collected and creation of the dossier, including the planning of the future governance of the area. In phase 2) objectives taken from the action plans of the national Reserves were discussed with relevant stakeholders and specified: for instance objectives on the conservation of large carnivores were substantially modified following the interaction with farmers.³⁸ When asked about the relative importance of conservation in the UNESCO MAB scheme, the interviewee responded that these reserves have to pursue three sets of objectives that are on the same level, meaning that none of them weighs more: conservation, development, and logistic support (the latter including training, research, education, etc.). Italian MAB Biosphere Reserves are usually managed by parks because the MAB national committee is part of the MASE (Ministry of Environmental Protection and Energy Security). Conservation must remain a job for the parks in this scheme. Biosphere Reserves should therefore promote the development of local communities in a way that does not endanger environmental quality. If the Julian Alps wanted to extend the Biosphere Reserve to Austria, it would be necessary first

— ³⁶ CIPRA International (2009) Final Report *Ecological network in the Alps: defining criteria and objectives for pilot region*, available at https://www.alpconv.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Fotos/Banner/Organisation/thematic_working_bodies/Part_01/ecological_network_platform/9_Pilotregion_e-2.pdf

³⁷ There are also reserves that are created at transboundary level, but these are called “transnational”. When national reserves preexist, they can instead decide to add the transboundary level, like in the Julian Alps but also for Monviso.

³⁸ Please note that Italian and Slovenian farmers interviewed (1 and 1) said that they were not involved in the development of the candidature.

to create a national Biosphere Reserve in Austria (or that one of the existing national Reserves includes some Austrian territories – highly improbable) and then to create another candidature to include the Austrian Reserve in the existing transboundary Reserve. This would take at least 5 years if Austrians were to start this process already in 2024. Thus the process is burdensome and time-consuming.

Int_JulianAlps_11_LA_IT: The interviewee highlighted the different roles of the PNPG Management Board members. The representatives nominated by the FVG Region are experts, represent a reference point, and give inputs on how to operate. The municipalities' representatives have a political role since they know local issues and have a privileged view of their areas. Local issues and views need to be combined with the input provided by the regional experts and economic stakeholders. Youth is the main hope for the area. Their role has been strengthened in the PNPG through the formal recognition of the YC as an independent body with dedicated funds. The YC can manage these funds autonomously, which enabled them to grow further. The work and investment that the PNPG is making on youth are widely recognized, for instance, within EUROPARC, despite it being a small park. The involvement of youth was based on two pillars: 1) making youth aware of the PNPG for its natural value, not as an amusement park; 2) preparing them to become future administrators sensitive to territorial needs. This action on youth is additional to the activities done with schools, which is a broader effort where you target one hundred pupils and two may be interested eventually. The interviewee spoke about cooperation with AT as well. The PNPG is starting to cooperate with AT protected areas like the Nockberge and Dobratsch. In this context, municipalities can operate through GALs, and this is happening in other areas of FVG, close to Gorizia and Trieste. Another aspect that emerged relates to the peculiarity of the Resia area (which is the biggest municipality contributing to the area of the PNPG) in terms of traditions and linguistic identity. It was highlighted that most of the PNPG staff are also local people (from Resia), know directly the issues addressed, and possess the cultural, traditional, and linguistic sensitivities characteristic of this area. Therefore, they know how to operate and behave in this context since they are aware of the ideological and political consequences of some initiatives/actions.

Int_JulianAlps_13_NA_SI: The interviewee emphasized the importance of regional initiatives in shaping national strategies and contributing to long-term conservation goals.

Int_JulianAlps_14_NA_SI: The interviewee also highlighted the importance of mechanisms such as expert working groups and platforms like the ABB within the Alpine Convention framework. These bodies facilitate monitoring biodiversity, promoting ecological connectivity, and aligning efforts with global biodiversity goals like the Kunming-Montreal Framework. The interviewee underscored that these mechanisms (working groups and platforms) are both formal and informal, involving extensive collaboration with contracting parties, observers, and local stakeholders. However, challenges such as differing national legislations and protection regimes across borders were recognized as barriers to effective implementation. The interviewee noted that Slovenia's presidency of the Alpine Convention includes priorities like conservation, connectivity, and restoration, with ongoing efforts to translate these into action plans. EUSALP complements these efforts by fostering cross-border ecological connectivity and integrating biodiversity considerations into broader spatial planning policies.

Int_JulianAlps_16_CS_OI_IT: This interviewee recounted the story of the creation of the PNPG. As explained in section 2.2 hunters played a major role here. Their vision however was different from how the park developed shortly after its creation. They had imagined a model of a huge park of 30,000 hectares that contained a strict reserve where hunting was prohibited more or less coinciding with the current territory of the park (6,500-7,000 hectares of strict reserve compared to the 9,000 hectares currently existing). The interviewee had managed to make the regional council of FVG approve an amendment to

the original law instituting the big park³⁹. This amendment allowed for the selection hunting of ungulates within the territory of the park. The interviewee lamented a biased media coverage of the news that was represented by local media as hunting entering the parks, thus spreading misinformation. Environmental associations then asked for a referendum on this amendment, and although the referendum was a fiasco, the project of a big park was abandoned due to changes in national and regional legislation and in political leadership. Hunters originally had different plans also concerning who should be responsible for monitoring in the park's territory: for them monitoring and patrolling had to be performed by park guards rather than from regional forest guards as it then happened. The current regional law instituting the PNPG is in the view of the interviewee a copy of the national law, which is problematic because it alienates the park from the people.

Int_JulianAlps_17_OI_SI: The interviewee criticized the political nature of leadership appointments at TNP as this often-prioritized political loyalty over expertise, which undermines the park's ability to effectively address biodiversity challenges. This constitutes barrier to effective governance, suggesting that politically motivated appointments undermined expertise and long-term planning.

Int_JulianAlps_18_ES_Y_SI: The interviewee highlighted a disconnect between public perceptions of wildlife conservation (focused on benefits) and the realities faced by local farmers. They criticized EU policies on wolf management and emphasized the need for balanced approaches that consider economic, social, and environmental factors.

Int_JulianAlps_19_ES_SI: The interviewee highlighted the importance of fostering a shared understanding of sustainability, which they argued is often misunderstood or overused as a concept. The interviewee cited a planned event in London to promote the region's biodiversity and sustainable tourism, showcasing cross-border collaboration in areas like cycling tourism.

Int_JulianAlps_21_PM_LA_IT: In the interview, it emerged that the composition of the PNPG Management Board may change frequently due to the different timing of the elections in the park municipalities as well as the nomination of the FVG Region's representatives. The interviewee mentioned that there are exchanges and good neighboring relations with SI municipalities bordering the Canin area, but this aspect was not explicitly linked to the cooperation between the parks.

Int_JulianAlps_22_CS_IT: The interviewee said that the only real glacier currently existing in the Julian Alps is the *Montasio occidentale* (Western Montasio) glacier, which however is located at an altitude of only 1800-1900 m.

³⁹ The interviewee mentioned regional law No. 11, but could not remember the exact year. Probably of 1983, when the first law was approved according to the PNPG's website: <https://www.parcoprealpigiulie.it/it/principale/territorio/storia#:~:text=Il%20Parco%20naturale%20regionale%20delle,cammino%20durato%20oltre%20due%20decenni.>

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